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PERCEIVE

**Perceptive Enhanced Realities of Colored collections
through AI and Virtual Experiences**

D7.2 Assessment of Tools, Services and Prototypes

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Executive Summary

Deliverable D7.2 reports how the PERCEIVE evaluated the project’s tools, platform services, and prototypes in real-world settings, translating the evaluation strategy defined in D7.1 into implemented protocols, field campaigns, and analysed results. The report explicitly separates *algorithmic/technical verification* (addressed in WP4/WP5 deliverables) from *perceptual, cognitive/emotional, functional, and experiential efficacy* assessed in WP7: the “quantitative” evidence here is primarily psychometric and usability data, complemented by structured qualitative feedback, because “ground truth” reference states rarely exist for heritage colour reconstruction and degradation scenarios.

1) What was evaluated. D7.2 covers two complementary assessment streams: (i) **Tools and services** (Section 7.2.1) and (ii) **Prototypes/demonstrators** (Section 7.2.2). Together, they validate whether PERCEIVE outputs are *usable, understandable, trusted, and valuable* for the project’s main target groups—heritage professionals and researchers—while also probing how effectively demonstrators convey scientific content and foster engagement (including “care”, authenticity, and participation goals).

2) Methodological approach. Across campaigns, user feedback was collected mainly via **on-site structured questionnaires** plus **observation** and, in some cases, guided interactions. Quantitative reporting follows a consistent rule: calculations are performed on a “**Users Only**” subset and summarised as means and “% positive” ratings. Qualitative answers are grouped into recurring themes to identify pain points and prioritise actionable improvements (“quick wins”). For one tool (StyleShade3D), a dedicated instrument was used. The prototype evaluations also include ethical compliance statements.

3) Key results: assessment of tools and (platform) services. **Tool evaluation outcomes** are reported per tool, based largely on a campaign with a specialised audience (notably at Digital Heritage 2025). Overall, respondents frequently had prior conservation/diagnostics knowledge, aligning well with PERCEIVE’s intended professional user base.

Highlights and findings:

- **High satisfaction and strong perceived value** emerged for several tools but often paired with requests for: (a) clearer in-app explanations for non-experts, (b) higher-resolution/zoom inspection, (c) better preservation of fine detail/texture and avoidance of artefacts, (d) improved performance (speed), and (e) stronger interoperability (uploads, APIs/IIIF).
- **Trust/acceptability** was generally strengthened when outputs were framed as *interpretive* and accompanied by transparency about assumptions and limitations.

Examples of tool-specific takeaways

- **Degreening:** strong acceptance and perceived effectiveness in reducing green cast, with improvement priorities around artefact avoidance, grain/detail preservation, and inspection/UI (zoom), plus interoperability (uploads/IIIF).
- **doLCE 2.0 (lenticular reconstruction):** very high satisfaction with experience and resulting colour, while users asked for better guidance/tooltips, more intuitive automation, sharper output, and faster processing.
- **LDE (Light Damage Estimator):** strong interface satisfaction, but mixed usefulness; users requested clearer explanation of the dual-method setup, more modelling factors (e.g., humidity/pollutants/outdoor contexts), better inspection/reporting, and upload options; processing speed was the main UX weakness.
- **MulaX + AVS and SimTex:** very positive reception, paired with calls for richer scientific context, stronger “expert mode”/transparency, improved realism/fidelity, and better comparison/export features.
- **Text2Autochromes:** perceived as enjoyable and promising but needing clearer prompt guidance and improved fidelity to authentic autochrome visual signatures (notably grain) before routine professional use.
- **CKR (Colour Knowledge Repository):** usability and search were rated positively, while perceived professional usefulness depended strongly on content breadth; users asked for expanded datasets/resource types and lower barriers to access.

4) Reconstruction and “metric realism” in heritage contexts. A dedicated section addresses how PERCEIVE meets the Grant Agreement’s reconstruction-evaluation expectations in the absence of real-world “ground truth.” It includes a comparative analysis of two independent colour-change prediction approaches

(photochemical vs statistical) within LDE, assessed in perceptual/colourimetric terms (CIELAB-based comparisons over exposure ranges mapping to decades of museum display). The conclusion is that both models produce coherent, qualitatively consistent trends suitable for decision-support scenarios, while acknowledging limits of validation when datasets overlap with development data.

5) Key results: assessment of prototypes and demonstrators. D7.2 reports field evaluations of demonstrators, including where and how they were deployed, who participated, and what was learned about usability, engagement, and knowledge transfer.

Campaign contexts

- **InArt24 (2024)** in Oslo: evaluation of two demonstrators—the Scream Time Machine and the Autochrome Viewer—across conference and museum contexts.
- **Digital Heritage Expo 2025:** wider evaluation activity, including PERCEIVE prototypes and tools; the “Perceive Isis’ Colours” exhibition is documented as being awarded a best-expo prize by visitors in that context.
- Follow-ups for “Perceive Isis’ Colours” at **Archeovirtual 2025** in Paestum and a current setup at the **ERIHS Central Hub** in Florence.

Demonstrators and Prototypes’ findings:

- **Scream Time Machine:** strong engagement especially in tactile/high-resolution exploration and the social gameplay component; challenges included comprehension of chronological ordering and the need for clearer guidance and improved audio/communication design.
- **Autochrome Viewer:** users generally understood the interaction, with curiosity/expectation common; usability improvements centred on clearer wayfinding (“look here” cues), more contextual explanation of autochromes, better alignment/stability of viewing elements, and clarity about restoration/inpainting intent.
- **Perceive Isis’ Colours – Echoes of Loss:** results indicate cognitive and emotional involvement, learning of the reconstruction pipeline, and measurable shifts in some “care” intentions and perceived efficacy, based on paired pre/post questionnaires across venues.
- **Perceive Isis’ Colours –Gifts of Isis:** results indicate that the social component has a significant impact in the perception of authenticity and that has also a connection with the sense of presence and perception of the atmosphere and engagement, while the self components, especially those related to knowledge acquisition are strengthened by single user interaction, more than by multi-player.

6) Metrological evaluation: colour accuracy in projection-based AR. Beyond user studies, D7.2 includes a Spectro radiometric assessment of colour deviations in a projection-mapping setup used to visualise reconstructed polychromy on a 3D-printed replica within the Echoes of Loss exhibit. Measurements show systematic deviations (e.g., increased lightness and shifts in chromatic components) when projecting without compensation for surface reflectance—even on a nominally “white” replica—supporting future work on compensation strategies for more faithful appearance reproduction, especially if projecting onto non-uniform materials or original objects.

Document History

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Section 7.2.1

Assessment of Tools and Services

7.2.1.1 Scope and Relationship to Technical Deliverables

This assessment distinguishes between algorithmic performance (covered in WP4) and perceptual/functional efficacy (the focus of WP7). While Deliverable D4.1 (IBR & Training Data) and D5.2 (PERCEIVE Platform) provide the quantitative technical verification of the AI models—reporting on loss functions, synthetic data generation (e.g., Text2Autochrome), and infrastructure latency—this deliverable (D7.2) focuses on the practitioner's reception of these outputs. Therefore, the "quantitative" data presented here refers to psychometric user feedback (Likert-scale satisfaction, usability scores, trust metrics) rather than computer vision metrics (like PSNR/SSIM). As established in the Grant Agreement, where "ground truth" reference images for historical artifacts do not exist, this assessment prioritizes qualitative expert validation over theoretical error rates.

7.2.1.2 Evaluation method summary

User feedback was collected primarily through structured online questionnaires administered on-site. The evaluation methodology combines quantitative usability metrics with qualitative thematic analysis to provide a holistic view of tool readiness.

Quantitative Analysis For each tool, headline results are reported based on Likert-scale questions (1–5). To ensure data validity, quantitative calculations (means and percentage of positive ratings) are computed exclusively on the "Users Only" subset, filtering out respondents who did not directly interact with the specific tool. Key dimensions measured include:

- *Satisfaction & Aesthetics: Visual appeal, ease of navigation, and overall user satisfaction.*
- *Perceived Usefulness: The likelihood of adopting the tool in professional workflows or research contexts.*
- *Trust & Acceptability: Confidence in the scientific validity of the results and the transparency of the process.*
- *Qualitative Analysis Open-ended feedback was aggregated and grouped into recurring themes (e.g., "Interaction Improvements," "Accuracy Concerns") to identify specific pain points and prioritize "quick wins" for future development cycles.*

Note on Reconstruction Metrics While the Grant Agreement suggests the use of quantitative image quality metrics (such as PSNR and SSIM) where possible, these metrics require a "ground truth" reference image—the original, un-faded artwork—which typically does not exist for real-world heritage objects. Consequently, in cases where ground truth is unavailable, this assessment relies on qualitative expert inspection and perceptual evaluation rather than full-reference degradation metrics. Technical reporting on theoretical performance using synthetic datasets is covered separately in WP4 deliverable

7.2.1.3 Tool Specific Evaluation Results

Giorgos Papadopoulos (FORTH ICS), Paschalis Paderis (FORTH ICS)

This section reports the specific results for each tool collected during the evaluation campaigns. The assessment engaged a highly specialised audience: across all tools, the majority of respondents possessed prior professional knowledge of conservation or diagnostic analysis. The demographic breakdown (Table 1) confirms that the evaluation successfully reached the project's primary target groups: Academic Researchers (TG2) and Cultural Heritage Professionals (TG1).

Table 1: Summary of participants and Professional Profiles per Tool (DH25 Siena)

Tool Name	Sample (N)	Primary Sector: Academia & Research	Primary Sector: Cultural Heritage (Museums)	Prior Conservation Knowledge*
SimTex	30	63%	17%	57%
LDE	24	54%	29%	67%
doLCE 2.0	21	65%	10%	70%
MulaX +AVS	19	63%	25%	94%
StyleShadeD	19	45% (Students)	35%	68%
Degreening	18	55%	22%	72%
Text2Autochromes	6	66%	17%	83%
CKR	5	60%	20%	80%
TOTAL	142	~59%	~22%	High¹

*Percentage of respondents answering "Yes" to prior knowledge of conservation/diagnostics.

Figure 1: Distribution of Professional Sectors by Tool

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7.2.1.3.1 Degreening App

Sample

A total of N=18 responses were collected. N=15 respondents indicated they used the tool, while N=3 indicated they did not (but still filled in the questionnaire). Participants were primarily from Academia (majority) with additional respondents from the cultural sector and related professional roles.

Quantitative results (users only, N=15)

- Satisfaction with the experience: mean 4.4/5, 80% positive
- Green cast reduction while preserving characteristic rendering/grain: mean 4.33/5, 86.7% positive
- Avoidance of misleading artefacts (halos, oversmoothing, false detail): mean 3.93/5, 66.7% positive
- Acceptability for scholarly publication (if fully disclosed): mean 4.4/5, 93.3% positive
- Retention of fine details/textures: mean 4.07/5, 73.3% positive

Perceived usefulness (users only, N=15)

86.7% of users considered the tool useful either as-is or with modifications (8 “as-is”, 5 “modified”), while 13.3% (2 users) considered it “not useful”.

Qualitative feedback

Open comments converge on a small set of recurring improvement points:

1. Resolution / grain structure preservation. Several respondents asked for improved grain detail and less smoothing/blur to better preserve fine texture and avoid misleading interpretation.
2. Upload / interoperability features. Requests include uploading one’s own images and/or offering IIIF support or broader API deployment options.
3. Accuracy and robustness. Suggestions include increasing training data and improving correction precision in small-detail areas; also handling other degradation types (e.g., overexposure).
4. Interaction improvements. Requests include zoom functionality and better inspection tools for evaluating before/after results in detail.

Conclusions

Overall, DH25 Siena feedback indicates strong acceptance for research communication and publication (with disclosure) and high perceived effectiveness in reducing green cast while retaining the characteristic look of autochromes. The main risk area is artefact avoidance and fine-detail retention, where a non-trivial fraction of users flagged oversmoothing or insufficient precision. These results support prioritizing:

1. higher-resolution output / grain-preserving processing
2. zoom and inspection UI
3. upload + interoperability (IIIF/API) to increase real-world uptake

7.2.1.3.2 CKR – Colour Knowledge Repository

Sample

A total of N=5 responses were collected. All respondents indicated they used the CKR. Participants were mainly from Academia (3/5), with additional representation from the Cultural Sector (1/5) and

Students (1/5). All respondents were in the 40–65 age group. Roles included researcher/academic, museum professional, technician/engineer, student, and manager.

Quantitative results (users, N=5)

- Ease of navigation / user-friendliness: mean 4.0/5, 80% positive
- Search effectiveness (finding relevant datasets/resources): mean 4.0/5, 80% positive
- Metadata fields enable meaningful description: mean 3.8/5, 80% positive
- Usefulness for research/professional activities: mean 3.0/5, 40% positive

Fit to needs

Three respondents stated that CKR resource types meet their needs, while two answered “Not sure”. One respondent requested additional resource types, specifically digital microscopy data.

Community features (interest & motivation)

Respondents expressed interest in joining communities around topics such as Colour changes in paintings (selected by all), as well as Historical photography collections, Lost polychromy on sculptures, and fading of textiles. Key motivations to participate in CKR communities included data sharing, sharing best analysis practices, data reuse, data management, and use of data for research purposes.

Likelihood to recommend

Most respondents indicated they would recommend CKR to colleagues (3 “Very likely”, 1 “Somewhat likely”), while one response was “Very unlikely”.

Qualitative feedback

Open comments converge on the following improvement points:

1. Expand content coverage. Requests include expanding the database with more spectroscopic data of artworks and including more artefacts/monuments.
2. Lower barriers to access. A user asked for more login options, noting that not all potential users have ORCID.
3. Make CKR friendlier for Art Historians. A respondent requested clearer terminology, e.g., using common pigment names alongside chemical notation (e.g., “Silver” vs “Ag”), to support non-technical audiences.
4. Add new data types. A specific suggestion was to include digital microscopy data as a supported/available resource type.

Conclusions

Feedback suggests that CKR is perceived as easy to navigate with an effective search function, and metadata is generally considered adequate by most users. However, perceived usefulness for day-to-day professional/research work is more mixed (mean 3.0/5), indicating that CKR’s value likely depends on content breadth and domain fit.

Priority improvements emerging from users are:

1. expanding datasets (especially spectroscopy + broader artefacts/monuments),
2. improving access/login options,
3. strengthening interpretability for non-technical users, and diversifying login options beyond ORCID to improve accessibility.

7.2.1.3.3 doLCE 2.0 – Lenticular Colour Reconstruction

Sample

A total of N=21 responses were collected. N=20 respondents evaluated the tool (either through direct use or guided demonstration), while N=1 indicated they did not (but still completed the questionnaire). Respondents came primarily from Academia (13/20 users), with additional participation from the Cultural Sector (6/20) and ICT (1/20). Roles included researcher/academic, heritage/conservation scientist, museum professional, technician/engineer, developer, designer, and management roles.

Quantitative results (users only, N=20)

- Satisfaction with the experience: mean 4.55/5, 90% positive
- Satisfaction with the resulting colour: mean 4.45/5, 95% positive
- Perceived accuracy of the resulting colour (categorical): 45% “Yes”, 55% “Maybe”
- Helpfulness of lenticular colour reconstruction in workflow: mean 3.55/5, 55% positive
- Usefulness in the respondent’s field (categorical): 40% “useful as-is”, 40% “useful with modifications”, 20% “not useful” (overall useful: 80%)

Qualitative feedback

1. More explanation and guidance for non-experts: several respondents asked for short explanations/tooltips on lenticular film/Kodacolor principles and clearer guidance on what controls/flags (e.g., “final frame”) mean, especially for unassisted use.
2. Improve interaction and automation: requests include making the UI more intuitive (e.g., automatically re-render after selecting options without extra steps) and adding interactive explanations within the tool.
3. Performance and output quality: recurring points were faster inference times, sharper output (avoid “washed out/smoothed” look), and better preservation of fine detail/texture (including the “textual structure” visible in the original).
4. Extended functionality: suggestions include rendering all uploaded frames and viewing motion/video directly in the app, supporting non-lenticular images, and improving noise filtering/background handling.

Conclusions

User feedback shows strong satisfaction with the overall experience and resulting colour (means >4.4/5), while perceived workflow helpfulness is more moderate (mean 3.55/5). Perceived accuracy is mostly positive but cautious (55% “Maybe”), suggesting users want clearer transparency/explanation to build confidence. Overall usefulness is high (80% “useful” either as-is or with modifications).

Improvement priorities centred on:

1. better in-app guidance for non-experts
2. smoother interaction (less manual intervention)
3. faster processing
4. improved detail preservation and sharpness of the reconstructed output

7.2.1.3.4 Light Damage Estimator (LDE)

Sample

A total of N=24 responses were collected. Respondents were primarily from Academia (13/24) and the Cultural Sector (7/24), with additional participation from Creative Industries (2/24), ICT (1/24), and other sectors (1/24). Most participants reported prior knowledge of conservation/diagnostic analysis in cultural heritage (16/24 “Yes”).

Quantitative results (N=24)

Aesthetics was rated on a 1–5 scale. “User-friendliness / processing speed / intuitive usability / image resolution” were collected as categorical ratings (Very low–Very high) and are summarized here on an equivalent 1–5 mapping (Very low=1, Very high=5). “% positive” = 4–5.

- Satisfaction with interface aesthetics: mean 4.33/5, 91.7% positive
- User-friendliness: mean 4.00/5, 87.5% positive
- Processing speed: mean 3.33/5, 37.5% positive (majority responses were Neutral)
- Intuitive usability: mean 4.04/5, 83.3% positive
- Resolution of displayed images: mean 4.00/5, 75.0% positive

Perceived usefulness in the respondent’s field (N=24)

- Useful already in the current version: 7/24 (29.2%)
- Useful, but in a modified version: 9/24 (37.5%)
- Not useful: 8/24 (33.3%)

Overall, 16/24 (66.7%) consider the tool useful (as-is or with modifications).

Intended frequency of use (N=24)

- One time only: 9/24 (37.5%)
- Monthly: 5/24 (20.8%)
- Yearly: 4/24 (16.7%)
- Weekly: 3/24 (12.5%)
- Never: 3/24 (12.5%)

Preferred visualization mode (N=24)

- Side-by-side comparison between two predictions: 10/24 (41.7%)
- Toggle between current state and faded version: 7/24 (29.2%)
- New and faded colorants view: 5/24 (20.8%)
- Library of predictions: 2/24 (8.3%)

The ‘preferred visualisation mode’ item captures which comparison view users would choose as their primary way to inspect predictions (single-choice). Therefore, lower percentages do not indicate lower usability or lower perceived quality; they indicate that some modes are more default-friendly in time-limited, in-situ demonstrations. The ‘library of predictions’ view is also cognitively heavier (it requires browsing multiple outputs), so it naturally attracts fewer selections in a booth setting. Results suggest prioritising side-by-side and toggle views as default presentation modes, while retaining ‘library of predictions’ as an optional/advanced view for expert workflows.

Qualitative feedback

1. Explanation and guidance for non-experts. Multiple respondents note that the presence of two scientific methods can be confusing without clearer explanation; suggestions include guidance

tables, clearer descriptions, and simplifying the presentation (e.g., showing one method by default).

2. Broader modelling factors and contexts. Users requested that the estimator account for additional decay factors (e.g., humidity/air pollutants) and extend beyond controlled environments (e.g., outdoor exposure scenarios).
3. Content coverage and interoperability. Recurrent requests include expanding the available artworks/materials and allowing users to upload their own images/artefacts for estimation.
4. Inspection and output reporting. Users asked for better image inspection (zoom, higher effective resolution), clearer/complete result reporting, and additional quantitative output indicators (e.g., “percentage difference” between before and predicted result, explicit time reporting).
5. Trust and validation concerns. Some comments highlight the lack of “ground truth” for validating realism/accuracy, which affects confidence in interpreting results.
6. Inverse Simulation: Respondents expressed interest in a 'reverse' workflow: rather than just fading a pristine model, they wish to input a currently faded artifact and have the tool to hypothesize the original colors.

Conclusions

Feedback indicates strong satisfaction with interface aesthetics, user-friendliness, and intuitive usability, while processing speed is the main UX weakness (most responses are neutral rather than positive). Perceived usefulness is mixed but overall positive (66.7% useful as-is or with modifications).

The most consistently requested improvements are:

1. clearer guidance (especially around the two-method setup)
2. broader modelling factors (humidity/pollutants/outdoor contexts)
3. expanded artwork coverage and user uploads
4. stronger inspection/output reporting (zoom, clearer results, quantitative change indicators).

7.2.1.3.5 MulaX + AVS

Sample

A total of N=19 responses were collected. N=16 respondents indicated they used the tool, while N=3 indicated they did not (but still completed the questionnaire). Among users (N=16), most participants were from Academia (10/16), followed by Cultural Sector / cultural-sector-and-student (4/16), with additional participation from Creative Industries (1/16) and Students (1/16). Prior knowledge of conservation/diagnostic analysis in the CH domain was high: 15/16 users answered “Yes”.

Quantitative results (users only, N=16)

- Satisfaction with the experience: mean 4.56/5, 100% positive
- Helpfulness of diagnostic-technique filtering in workflow: mean 4.31/5, 87.5% positive
- Ability to distinguish analysis/technique types on the 3D visualisation: mean 4.13/5, 87.5% positive
- Need for a legend to understand types, colours and numbers of analyses: mean 4.25/5, 81.25% positive
- Effectiveness of “Discovery Layers” mode (Lens and Split): mean 4.69/5, 100% positive

Perceived usefulness in the respondent’s field (users only, N=16)

- Useful already in the current version: 9/16 (56.25%)
- Useful, but in a modified version: 3/16 (18.75%)

- Not useful: 4/16 (25.0%)

Overall, 12/16 (75.0%) consider the tool useful (as-is or with modifications).

Recall of key functionality (users only, N=16)

When asked how many left-menu functions they remembered using during exploration:

- 13/16 (81.25%) reported using two functions (Discovery Layers and Explore Analysis)
- 3/16 (18.75%) reported using only one function (Discovery Layers)

Qualitative feedback

1. More explanation and context for non-experts. Several comments request clearer explanation of layer types and analysis techniques (what each mode means, what the analysis represents), and better context around semantic maps and documentation to support both specialists and general audiences.
2. Access to richer scientific content. Requests include adding) and scientific/spectroscopic data, improving how hyperspectral information is presented (fewer, more meaningful wavelengths; more compositional maps), and generally strengthening the scientific interpretability of what is shown.
3. Interaction and inspection improvements. Users suggested higher-resolution rendering/zoom, the ability to “stop” or interact without constrained radius behavior, and the ability to download snapshots of layers for reference or further study.
4. Capture, cataloguing and archiving. There were requests related to better cataloguing/archiving of uploaded media and extending information coverage across the whole model more automatically.

Conclusions

Feedback indicates very high satisfaction and strong perceived effectiveness of the Discovery Layers functionality. Most users found diagnostic filtering helpful and reported they could distinguish technique types on the 3D visualization; many also indicated a legend is needed, supporting the inclusion of clearer UI guidance and interpretive context. Perceived usefulness is positive overall (75% useful as-is or with modifications).

Improvement priorities cantered on:

1. clearer explanations and contextualization of analyses/layers
2. stronger access to and presentation of scientific/spectroscopic content
3. improved inspection and export features (zoom/high-res renders, downloadable layer snapshots, and better archiving workflows).

7.2.1.3.6 SimTex

Sample

A total of N=30 responses were collected. Respondents were primarily from Academia (19/30), with additional participation from the Cultural Sector (5/30), ICT (2/30), and single responses from Student-only, Cultural Sector and Student, Research, and Engineering. Prior knowledge of conservation/diagnostic analysis in the CH domain was reported by 17/30 respondents (“Yes”).

Quantitative results (N=30)

- Satisfaction with the experience: mean 4.40/5, 96.7% positive
- Item with anchors “Not at all aligned” → “Perfectly aligned”: mean 3.63/5, 63.3% positive

- Item with anchors “Not at all” → “A great deal”: mean 4.23/5, 80.0% positive
- Item with anchors “Not at all” → “Very much”: mean 4.33/5, 93.3% positive

Perceived usefulness in the respondent’s field (N=30)

- Yes, already in this current version: 11/30 (36.7%)
- Yes, but in a modified version: 11/30 (36.7%)
- Not useful: 8/30 (26.7%)

Overall, 22/30 (73.3%) consider the tool useful (as-is or with modifications).

Qualitative feedback

1. Stronger “expert mode” and transparency: respondents requested the ability to inspect more technical details (e.g., spectral curves), and more information about hypotheses/segments so users understand what they are looking at and that outputs are interpretive.
2. Improve realism and fidelity: several comments point to the abstraction/simplicity of the segmentation visualization and ask for improved texture/material realism (e.g., better fabric detail when zooming in) and higher detail/fidelity overall.
3. Better UI guidance: repeated requests for captions/tooltips and clearer explanations of buttons and parameters (including contextual help and clearer parameter meaning).
4. Comparison and exploration features: suggestions include clearer time-evolution views of fading, the ability to compare multiple states (past vs future / faded vs unfaded), adjusting illumination or adding a movable light source, saving snapshots for later comparison, and supporting more dynamic/expressive visualization (e.g., cloth movement).
5. Validation and scope: some respondents noted they would need testing on a larger number of artefacts and/or additional colours/material cases to strengthen confidence and applicability.
6. Inverse Workflow: Users requested a 'reverse' mode to hypothesize the original colors of currently faded artifacts, rather than only simulating future fading.

Conclusions

Overall satisfaction with SimTex is high (mean 4.40/5), and the majority of respondents (73.3%) consider it useful (as-is or with modifications). Responses suggest that the core concept is well received.

Improvements should focus on:

1. increased transparency and expert inspection options (to support trust and interpretation)
2. higher realism/fidelity of the visual output (texture/detail, segmentation presentation)
3. clearer guidance for parameters and controls
4. stronger comparison features for exploring fading scenarios over time (including saving views for later reference)

7.2.1.3.7 Text2Autochromes

Sample

A total of N=6 responses were collected. All respondents indicated they used the tool. Participants were mainly from Academia (4/6), with one respondent from the Cultural Sector and one from Academia/Cultural roles; age groups were 25–40 (4/6) and 40–65 (2/6). Prior knowledge of conservation/diagnostic analysis in CH was reported by 5/6 respondents (“Yes”).

Quantitative results (users, N=6)

- Satisfaction with the experience: mean 3.50/5, 66.7% positive
- Perceived accuracy of generated results (labelled “Very accurate” in the questionnaire): mean 3.50/5, 66.7% positive
- Additional output-related item (1–5 scale): mean 3.17/5, 33.3% positive
- Acceptability (labelled “Highly acceptable” in the questionnaire): mean 3.83/5, 66.7% positive
- Perceived value (labelled “Highly valuable” in the questionnaire): mean 3.33/5, 50.0% positive

Perceived usefulness in the respondent’s field (N=6)

- Yes, already in this current version: 1/6 (16.7%)
- Yes, but in a modified version: 4/6 (66.7%)
- Not useful: 1/6 (16.7%)

Overall, 5/6 (83.3%) consider the tool useful (as-is or with modifications)

Qualitative feedback

1. Clarity and accessibility for non-expert users: comments note the interface may not make sense for users unfamiliar with generative AI (e.g., concepts like “seed”) and that what is expected in prompts is not sufficiently clear; suggestions include simplifying the UI to only essential inputs for general audiences.
2. Output fidelity to “real autochrome” characteristics: multiple respondents noted that generated images do not always resemble real autochromes (grain structure not visible/incorrect, images appear “too modern”, or requested scenes not coming through), even if the “vintage look” is appreciated.
3. Communicative/educational framing: one respondent described the tool as enjoyable but more like an engagement feature than a tool that clearly communicates autochromes or conservation issues, suggesting clearer interpretive framing if the goal is education rather than play.
4. Feature requests: requests include a zoom-in option and improving robustness to more complex prompts/scenes (e.g., people/animals).

Conclusions

Feedback indicates Text2Autochromes is generally perceived as enjoyable and potentially useful, but most respondents expect modifications before it can be reliably used in professional or interpretive contexts.

The main improvement priorities are:

1. clearer prompt guidance and a simplified interface for non-expert users
2. stronger fidelity to autochrome visual signatures (especially grain structure and avoiding a “modern” look)
3. better inspection/interaction features (e.g., zoom)
4. improved handling of complex scenes

7.2.1.3.8 StyleShade3D (dedicated user study – separate instrument)

Context **and** **method**

StyleShade3D were evaluated through an unmoderated in-situ user study at a digital-heritage conference booth, where participants explored the tool on a tablet and completed a digital questionnaire. The questionnaire included the UCL Museum Wellbeing Measures Toolkit GWQ (12 items), the Trust in Automation questionnaire (TiA), and four additional project-specific questions (Q33–Q36), with open-ended items and 1–7 rating items (higher scores indicate more positive responses).

Sample

N=19 voluntary participants (5 female, 14 male), average age 37.47 (SD 8.83). Participants self-rated as advanced in cultural heritage (mean 3.37/5) and advanced in digital technologies for cultural heritage (mean 3.94/5).

Quantitative results (GWQ and TiA; scale 1–7)

The GWQ results indicate an overall positive tone towards the experience. The highest GWQ mean score was for “feeling safe and secure” (Q4: mean 4.59, SD 0.51), while the lowest was “being amazed” (Q9: mean 3.47, SD 0.51), suggesting room to improve hedonic/engagement qualities. For the additional 1–7 items, participants rated as highly important both (i) the necessity of features for analysing and documenting changes in 3D models over time (Q34: mean 6.21, SD 0.85) and (ii) the importance of a mobile version for fieldwork or exhibitions (Q35: mean 6.41, SD 0.71).

Qualitative feedback

Feature requests and improvement suggestions concentrated on:

- clearer/annotated labels and more accurate pigment naming
- improved segmentation detail and higher 3D resolution
- lighting and inspection controls (moving light source, ambient occlusion, change illumination)
- richer interaction and comparison (ability to try different textures; an option to see the sculpture without colour; a chart showing other users’ colour choices)
- additional contextual information about the object accessible inside the interface

Conclusions

Overall results support good perceived safety/comfort and generally positive experience, with a clear signal that documentation-over-time features and mobile usage are priorities for real CH workflows.

The main improvement direction is:

1. to strengthen engagement (“amazed”)
2. add better inspection/lighting controls
3. improve clarity/precision in labels, segmentation, and object/context presentation

7.2.1.4 Evaluation of Services

The PERCEIVE Services constitute the foundational infrastructure layer of the platform, comprising eight specialized microservices, including Authorization, Identity, Orchestrator, Data, and Metadata services, that enable workflow orchestration and ensure compliance with FAIR principles. As detailed in D5.2 PERCEIVE Platform, these components function as the operational

backbone supporting the user-facing tools rather than direct end-user interfaces. Consequently, these services were not subject to the psychometric and usability observation studies conducted for the frontend tools in this deliverable. Instead, the evaluation of these services was conducted through technical validation against the project's Functional Requirements (FR) and Non-Functional Requirements (NFR). For the comprehensive reporting on these metrics, including response time efficiency and performance under load, please refer specifically to the Requirements Verification (Section 4.5) and Readiness Assessment sections of Deliverable D5.2.

7.2.1.5 Evaluation of Reconstructions

This section addresses the Grant Agreement requirement (Objective 3, KPI 3.4) regarding the comparative evaluation of reconstruction scenarios. WP7 assessed the available "Before/After" reconstruction cases to verify if the volume and quality of outputs meet the project's perceptual goals. Verification of the WP7 assessment confirms that the project has met the target of reconstruction cases through a combination of practitioner-evaluated real-world samples (assessed below) and technically validated synthetic datasets (reported in D4.1).

Evaluation of NTNU and IESL Colour-Change Predictions within the LDE Tool

The objective of this evaluation is to examine the suitability of the two independently developed colour-change prediction models used in the LDE tool, for assessing the long-term impact of museum illumination on historical pigments. The models considered are: (1) a photochemical model developed by IESL-FORTH, which is grounded in physically motivated ageing mechanisms, and (2) a statistical model developed by NTNU, which relies on data-driven relationships derived from experimental observations. Rather than ranking the models or identifying a superior approach, the intent of this analysis is to determine whether both models provide qualitatively consistent and quantitatively comparable predictions over time scales relevant to museum practice. Emphasis is placed on the coherence of predicted trends, the stability of dose-dependent behaviour, and the overall suitability of the models as decision-support tools for conservation planning. The analysed radiant exposure range ($\sim 7\text{--}34\text{ Wh/cm}^2$) corresponds approximately to 20 to 80 years of museum display, depending on illuminance level, daily exposure duration, and institutional conservation policies. This range captures typical long-term exhibition scenarios and allows the assessment of model behaviour from early-stage ageing through more advanced exposure conditions.

Methodology

Model predictions were evaluated in the CIELAB colour space (D65 illuminant, 2° standard observer), using colour differences expressed as ΔL^* , Δa^* , and Δb^* relative to a defined initial reference colour. Artificial ageing experimental data for the pigment Vermilion were used as a common basis for comparison at three representative radiant exposure levels: low ($\sim 7\text{ Wh/cm}^2$), mid (20 Wh/cm^2), and high ($\sim 33\text{ Wh/cm}^2$). The comparison focused on several complementary aspects: (i) the sign and direction of predicted colour changes, ensuring physical plausibility and consistency with known ageing behaviour; (ii) the relative contribution of lightness and chromatic components to the overall colour change; (iii) the smoothness and monotonicity of the predicted dose–response relationships across the examined exposure range. To provide a perceptual context for the numerical differences, the Euclidean distance in CIELAB space (ΔE_{1976}) between model predictions and experimental measurements was calculated. ΔE_{1976} is used here as an indicator of similarity between predicted and observed colour-change magnitudes, rather than as a strict acceptance or rejection criterion.

Figure 2: Experimental and model-predicted colour changes (Δ values) for Vermilion

Data and results

Figure... summarises the experimental colour-change measurements and the corresponding model predictions for Vermilion at the three exposure levels. For the highest exposure, model outputs at 34.24 Wh/cm² are compared with experimental data obtained at 33.1 Wh/cm²; this small mismatch is explicitly acknowledged and does not affect the qualitative interpretation of the results.

Across the full exposure range corresponding to several decades of museum illumination, both models predict the same qualitative ageing behaviour for Vermilion: progressive darkening ($\Delta L^* < 0$), systematic chromatic loss ($\Delta a^* < 0$ and $\Delta b^* < 0$), and a monotonic increase of colour change with radiant exposure. No sign reversals, abrupt changes, or non-physical trends are observed in either model. Quantitative differences between the models are primarily associated with the relative weighting of the chromatic components a* and b*, rather than with the overall magnitude or direction of colour change. Importantly, these differences do not alter the qualitative conclusions that would be drawn in a conservation context when comparing different illumination scenarios over long time horizons.

Conclusions

The comparative analysis indicates that both the photochemical model developed by IESL-FORTH and the statistical model developed by NTNU provide coherent and consistent predictions of long-term colour change for Vermilion under museum illumination conditions. Despite their different theoretical foundations, the models converge toward similar qualitative trends and

comparable orders of magnitude across exposure levels corresponding to approximately 20–80 years of display.

These findings support the acceptability of both models as predictive tools for long-term illumination impact assessment, risk evaluation, and scenario analysis in museum environments. While the Vermilion dataset used in this comparison was also employed during model development and thus does not constitute an independent validation, the observed cross-dose consistency provides confidence in the robustness of the predicted trends within the studied exposure range.

doLCE 2.0 - Evaluation old/new method

Comparisons of the lenticular colour reconstruction using the old method and the new method developed in PERCEIVE.

Figure 3: 36 comparisons of the results of the lenticular colour reconstruction using the new method developed in PERCEIVE (left) and the old method (right) that was the starting point of the research

Section 7.2.2

Assessment of Prototypes

1. Introduction (goals of the evaluation activities in PERCEIVE)

Alfonsina Pagano (CNR ISPC)

In PERCEIVE PROJECT we aim to address three main assumptions with concrete solutions:

1. **Make heritage science results accessible** for immediate use and further development to Creative Industry sectors as well as public of museums and exhibitions.
2. **Improve museums' curatorial approaches to the study of coloured collections** through a digital shared methodology and the use of digital practices to exhibit them.
3. **Widen the access and explore the use of coloured collections and digital artworks**, involving visitors and citizens, both inside and outside museums, improving their understanding and at the same time increasing their engagement with experiences that could be perceived as "authentic".

Beyond our good intentions, applied research efforts, and production activities, it is crucial to evaluate the user experience to validate the effectiveness of the PERCEIVE tools-services-prototypes we developed in the last months.

Important to say that PERCEIVE UX evaluations will be differentiated and customized according to each tool, service and prototype given the technicalities and artistic nature of them. Each author will follow a proper pipeline of development answering specific project goals related to 1-to-3 above mentioned assumptions.

Not all metrics and evaluation techniques will be widely applied. Tools and services will undergo a more technical and ergonomic inquiry, while prototypes (and demonstrators) will see technical but especially cognitive and social evaluation.

However, evaluation is a necessity in PERCEIVE PROJECT because, while the public is initially attracted to technological solutions, their attention towards historical information, cultural features or purely visual assets is often short-lived. Interest wanes quickly if the scientific content fails to maintain engagement or if interactions are cumbersome and unnatural. Therefore, it is imperative to reconsider digital technologies in relation with content, experience of usage and support. Colour reconstruction, authenticity, sense of care and Digital Art reliability counts on these aspects.

PERCEIVE strategy relies thus on **technical, cognitive and social analysis**. The emotional component is fundamental to every user and learning experience, as it motivates the use of digital applications. This motivation is what drives people to utilize AR/VR/XR and online products, which can activate the learning process more swiftly and in a contextually relevant manner ([Goleman, 1995](#)).

Another critical aspect to evaluate, and which PERCEIVE PROJECT will advocate, is **user engagement through gamification techniques**. Gamification has been chosen as an experiential model for several reasons:

- It emphasizes the role of the active user through a system guided by the user's choices and pace.
- It increases user engagement by setting objectives within the virtual exploration. This creates a strong motivation for the user, which is effective in focusing and concentrating on completing the immersive *coloured* experience.
- It promotes learning of polychromies, both directly and indirectly. Gamification strategies, design and co-creation activities facilitate user imagination and abstraction, focusing on specific information units.

1.1 PERCEIVE UX Evaluation: subject(s) of analysis

The objectives of the evaluation of the user experience (UX) in PERCEIVE PROJECT related to the experience of using tool-service-prototype developed to above-mentioned three assumptions.

PERCEIVE UX evaluation considered:

- The **product in its entirety**: instrumental qualities; usability tests are carried out (according to the [Nielsen/Norman guidelines](#));
- The **attitude and/or ability of the user and relative level of understanding of the contents**: instrumental / non-instrumental qualities; investigations relating to Pedagogical affordances are carried out;
- The **type of interaction with multimedia**: hedonic characteristics; accessibility, cognitive learning, and emotional stimulation tests are carried out ([ISO/Goleman](#)).

Fig¹. 4 – Infographics of the Typology of Evaluation used for PERCEIVE PROJECT. @A.Pagano, CNR ISPC

In the case of the *product* (1), the evaluation focused on the following motivations:

- Understanding whether the graphical interface (GUI) is well designed and highlights the correct functions, interactions and elements to be learned;
- Understand the effectiveness of the product's features in their entirety (functionality, usage times, usability, feasibility of use, accessibility ...);
- Verify whether the container (developed product) is suitable for the content (message to be transferred to user).

In the case of the *user* (2), the evaluation aimed to:

- Understand the educational benefits obtained during the use of the product;
- Test the user's capabilities during the use of the product;
- Deepen the knowledge of some direct and/or indirect learning mechanisms that occur with technological/multimedia products;
- Verify the reliability of a product in the Digital Heritage field.

Finally, in the case of *interaction* (3), the evaluation helped to clarify:

- Aspects of the interaction between system and user;
- Deepen the knowledge of the design features that most influence the interaction;
- Collect information relating to the interconnections between the cognitive mechanisms involved during the interaction;
- Obtain information on the technical qualities of the system used.

All PERCEIVE experiences were therefore subject to a double evaluation: of the context of use and of the digital/multimedia contents.

1.2 UX Evaluation Planning (see Del 7.1)

Evaluation tools

The PERCEIVE PROJECT used the **multi-partitioned analysis** as its operational methodology (Pagano et al., 2016). It is composed of **three evaluation tools** used according to a predetermined timeframe and a specific operating method. These tools allow for a more in-depth view of the user profiling and experience. They are:

- *Observation*: it is one of the most used at the beginning of each evaluation activity within the museum or in correspondence with a single multimedia installation, although it is not always easy to conduct (Kuniavsky, 2003); it is extremely useful as it provides fertile ground for the first considerations on users and technologies and for building the conceptual map for the investigative comparison of the results obtained from direct investigation tools. Observations are not only used at the beginning of the evaluation, but also during the user experience.
- *Questionnaire (or written Interview)*: it is essential to probe the basic knowledge of each user to identify the professional profile and education, establish needs and expectations, recognize attitudes, gestures, movements and comments of users (Garrett, 2002). The questionnaire is widely used in research and is constructed based on the purpose to be pursued (type of questions, modulation of sentences, level of language), and the function it must have within the scope of the project to be evaluated (usability test or demographic interest, customer satisfaction or cognitive learning, etc.); users can fill in the questionnaire autonomously, with a certain margin of expression.
- *Guided scenario*: it consists of direct communication between the operator and the user, where a series of information is recorded during the use of the multimedia product (Rubin and Chisnell, 2008); the sequence of questions that the operator must ask is predetermined and based on an increasing line of knowledge acquisition by the users - from the point of view of usability or recognition of contents and understanding - while enjoying the multimedia application or the museum visit. In PERCEIVE PROJECT this tool was partially used - at least in the first evaluation session in Oslo.

GENERAL PERCEIVE STRATEGY OF EVALUATION

used singularly, or combination of some of them, or all

THIS CHOICE NEEDS TO BE CUSTOMIZED ON EACH T-P-S PERCEIVE PRODUCT!

Fig. 5 – Infographics of the Strategy of Evaluation used for PERCEIVE PROJECT @A.Pagano, CNR ISPC

Nature of the investigative method

The multi-partitioned analysis involved both **quantitative and qualitative research**, different both in terms of the operating methods and the tools used:

- In the first case, the reflection on the collected data were based on many users questioned and, therefore, on the questionnaires; the percentage calculation of the answers and the cross-comparison, through statistical rules, will provide a general image of the trends related to the themes investigated.
- In qualitative research, on the other hand, the depth of the collected data was examined; the information units were cross-referenced, compared and grouped by similarity or divergence. The tools adopted was the observation, useful for understanding some aspects of the system-user interaction, investigating the impressions and comments reported by users regarding the experience. Visitors were asked to carry out and solve specific tasks; at the end of the interaction, the operator asked him some direct questions, to understand what problems may exist during the interaction, the logical-decisional process, the global evaluation of the experience and an analysis of the cognitive and emotional impact. With observation, the operator observed and recorded the user's behaviour in front of the digital application, without interfering in his decision-making process and with his actions.

In the multi-partitioned analysis, these tools often studied similar aspects, and their use was intentionally redundant, since it is functional to verify the level of sincerity of the user, the awareness and state of mind with which he will face and carry out his experience and, naturally, also the level of learning achieved.

Fig. 6 – Infographics of the Methodology of Evaluation used for PERCEIVE PROJECT. @A.Pagano, CNR ISPC

Logistics

The UX evaluation was submitted in **three moments**:

1. an *initial presentation moment*, for making the user understand the usefulness of this activity (for research and development purposes), its anonymity, the free nature of this test, and the freedom to refuse to be interviewed/observed.
2. a *second moment of use of the application* by the user; he/she was followed by the operator who observed his/her behaviours, his/her naturalness, his/her psycho-physical and verbal reactions, any discomforts and times of overall use.

3. a *third moment of direct and detailed evaluation*, where the operator spoke directly to the user, retracing some moments of the interaction and explaining some sensations felt.

The evaluation experience lasted **no more than 20 minutes**, from the moment of the meeting with the user until the closing of the questionnaire together with the operator.

The **operator**, during the entire evaluation activity, necessarily maintained an **impartial, non-influenceable and/or allusive-suggestive attitude regarding the questions or answers**. The same were formulated both on the questionnaire and verbally in a way that did not suggest what to say or mislead the user's idea.

Before the submission, all involved operators by PERCEIVE partners were provided with a training session about how to behave with users and how to conduct evaluation in public. A sort of **operative vademecum** were elaborated. Link to “**Manual of effective evaluator**” prepared by CNR ISPC for PERCEIVE PROJECT: <https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1D8QxShHkayU6Z-Kyc-p9Wluy6W3216RcJeA-AZUSuA/edit?usp=sharing>

Data were gathered from:

- “**Pre-experience**” **questionnaire (QST)**, where the demographics and profile of the user were collected before the interaction with the demonstrator
- “**During-experience**” **observation (OBS)**, hidden to the user, where the evaluation operators silently noticed the reactions of the users according to several predefined criteria
- “**Post-experience**” **questionnaire (QST)**, where the user was asked a set of questions about the quality of the experience.

Target

No type of user was selected a priori, to respect the randomness and variety of the public that can potentially reach the venue at any time and use the product.

The evaluation was carried out on a sample of about 50 users per each OBS and QST. This number was considered more than sufficient to draw up the first behavioural trends, comparable in the future with other evaluations. Furthermore, this number far exceeds the qualitative and quantitative standards set by the EU and ISO (which propose test cases with 15-20 participants).

Submission and UX templates

The UX evaluation was carried out via **laptops/tablets**, though and online service for collecting data in a unique repository.

It was composed of three evaluation moments (section 1.1.3) and each of them presents open and/or closed questions that are explained through the various investigative techniques (*see* templates in [Annex 1](#) and [Annex 2](#)).

The user was accompanied in filling out the “Post-experience” questionnaire by the operator, who instead conducted the “During the experience” and “Pre-experience” templates.

QST/Questionnaire

- First, the user’s personal details were annotated by operator or user himself: 5 single-choice questions, to outline their profile in summary.
- The “Pre-experience” section was about the user’s profiling from the point of view of cultural and habits. 5 single-choice and multiple-choice questions make up this section.
- The “Post-experience” section of the survey concerned the user's reflective activity after enjoying the content and the entire experiential context. 12 questions were asked to the user

directly by the operator: single-choice questions, multiple-choice questions, open questions, likert scale, image recognition and grid were presented to the user.

OBS/Observation

- First, the user's personal details were recorded by operator: 3 single-choice questions, to outline their profile in summary.
- The "During-experience" section was observed by operator and referred to the user's behaviour, attitudes, and comments while experiencing PERCEIVE content. The operator collected this data live, observing firsthand NOT interacting verbally with the user. This section is made up to 15 single and/or multiple-choice questions. Also open comments' section was present in the template.

PERCEIVE pipeline of work

PERCEIVE PROJECT partners followed a precise pipeline of work, presented in the below schema.

Fig. 7– Infographics of the Roadmap of Evaluation used for PERCEIVE PROJECT. @A.Pagano, CNR ISPC

1. Definition of Subject to be Evaluated:

- We began by clearly defining the subject of the evaluation. This step was crucial to establish the parameters and objectives of the evaluation.
- We identified the target group for the evaluation, ensuring it was representative of the project's end users.
- We decided whether the evaluation would take place in a controlled laboratory setting or a public space. Each option presented its specific advantages and challenges.

2. Construction of Evaluation Template:

- We established whether the evaluation would be quantitative, qualitative, or a combination of both. This decision depended on the nature of the data we aimed to collect and the insights we wanted to derive.
- Next, we constructed a customized evaluation templates. These were used to collect consistent and relevant data aligned with the predefined objectives.
- We determined whether to conduct a mid-term evaluation during the project or a final evaluation. This decision was based on the project's phase and the type of feedback needed.

- We decided on the tools for data collection: observations, interviews, questionnaires, or driven scenarios, or a combination of these. Each tool provided different types of valuable insights for the overall evaluation.
- We determined whether to use paper-based or digital methods (tablet/web-based) for data collection, based on what was most convenient and practical for the evaluation context.

3. *Submission of the Evaluation:*

- We planned how and where the collected evaluations would be submitted. This included the logistics of the submission location and the management of the collected data.
- We set the number of insights we wanted to obtain from participants to ensure a sufficiently large data base for analysis;
- We identified the operators who would conduct the evaluation, ensuring they had the necessary skills to interact with participants and collect accurate data.

4. *Data Collection and Analysis:*

- We defined the process for data collection and analysis, including the days dedicated to evaluation and the location where the data would be processed. We decided to use a shared platform to facilitate collaboration.
- We established the rules and calculation methods to be applied to the collected data to obtain meaningful results.

We planned how to use the results productively to improve the project. This included identifying the key performance indicators (KPIs) we aimed to achieve through this evaluation.

2. PERCEIVE Evaluation Sessions

2.1 “InArt24” Conference, Oslo (2024)

Irina Ciortan (NTNU), Irina CA Sandu (MUNCH), Arthur Clay (HSLU)

InART2024 was the 6th edition of the International Conference on Innovation in Art Research and Technology, that took place in Oslo, between the 4th and 7th of June. The scope of InArt24 is to build a bridge between natural sciences and conservation, which aligns with the interdisciplinary trait of the PERCEIVE project. For this reason, InArt24 was a venue for the submission and publication research contributions from several partners in the consortium. In addition to the scientific participation, the consortium decided to organize three collateral events to facilitate the dynamic exchange of information and good practices with the audience with a wide expertise in the cultural sector. These three collateral events were:

- **The organization of the PERCEIVE workshop** (under the coordination of Irina Sandu (MUNCH)), before the start of the conference, where research highlights of the project were presented to 75 attendees
- A special event for the **display of two PERCEIVE demonstrators** inside an **interactive room in a museum environment**, after the conference
- **Evaluation campaign of two PERCEIVE demonstrators** (under the coordination of WP7 leaders) in three different moments: pre-conference (during the workshop), during the conference, post-conference (at the museum).

2.1.1 Description of the case studies

2.1.1.1 The Scream Time Machine

The **Scream Time Machine** is an experience where we explore the surface of the painting (The Scream 1910?, MUNCH) and its colour changes (mainly for yellow and reds) with different senses.

At the present it has **3 main components**:

- 1) Tutorial as 2D animation and voice recording with subtitles in English** (a second version could also include subtitles in Norwegian for example). The tutorial has ca. 6 min length as a 2D animation showing the historical background of the Scream, the art techniques and evolution of the object's image along time, from around 1930 to the present (documented by the 2D scan and 3D prints) together with simulations of how color change could evolve in the future. This tutorial includes keywords and images that are going to be used for the third component.

Figure 8: video tutorial (can be visualized as a whole here: [Scenario2-Paintings - PERCEIVE \(perceive-horizon.eu\)](https://perceive-horizon.eu/Scenario2-Paintings))

- 2) Scream reinvented.** A set of 2 scan full size of the painting at 30x (Fig.2) and 3 areas with details of fading of the paint at 90x (Fig. 6 only shows 2 of them, 3D scans at 90x) that have been printed (as 2.5 prints) in a plastic material, monochrome and several polychrome versions of one of the details (head) provided as additional materials by Canon in collaboration with Hirox Europe company (Fig. 7);

Figure 9: 2D scan, 30x (provided as a link as it is heavy!)

3) **Board game** which uses images of the Scream for playing around the chronology of colour/image change. The game is made of 3 different decks (identified each with a colour for the background: *Dark blue* for *Playing cards* of the *Timeline*, *Red* for *Danger* cards, and *Green* for *Care* cards and also a dashboard (made of a cardboard having a colour similar to the one Scream is made on). The dark blue cards represent 8 digital photographs, B&W and coloured, of the Scream, taken in several years from 1938 to 2024. The game is designed to be used by min 2 players, one can be a *Danger Master* and all the rest *Time traveller(s)*.

Figure 10: Dashboard of the board game

1) Tutorial as 2D animation and voice recording

- The tutorial blends static images, video cuts (from other videos made during MOLAB 2017 and Dating Scream 2024 campaigns) and a voice recorded with explanation of each step moment relevant for the story. All steps of the acquisition of MOLAB (HSI and MA-XRF images) and Hirox 3D microscopic scans (2D + 3D details) were included in this 2D animation. It starts with images and text around the Ekely studio of Munch (the only one that is preserved on Munch's former estate) and ends with the blank dashboard representing the studio now, without furniture or pictures and the invitation to start the Board game.
- The story includes special moments in the life of the Scream (1910?) and also documentation and evidence of colour change studied with scientific tools. It will bring the visitor from the **Past** (around 1930) to the **Present** moment and then offer possibilities of **Future** exploration of the change in colour through hypotheses of simulation of this change in the future (JNF concept displayed as time slider).
- **Length** of the tutorial: 6.30 min.

2) Scream reinvented

- The **2D scan** and the **3D prints** of 2 selected areas show different aspects of the paint, the difference between the cardboard support and the paint, the areas where color fading has been detected, other degradation patterns on the surface and so on;
- The **B&W photo** from Ekely studio is one of the first photographic documentation of the Scream and the **3D prints** can be used for a different display of the painting surface and colours, using mirrors and light projections;
- Thus, the concept of **decay** and **unexpected events** that can damage a painting and its appearance, physical integrity and conservation condition (e.g. the theft) are explored by showing images of the Scream before and after the theft and also using the reversed

image of the painting to show how the print surface changes if a disruptive event happens during the printing process;

- End-users can **experience** through vision and touch the surface of the painting both on a TV screen, with zoom in and out functions, but also directly on the prints (monochromatic and coloured versions of the 3 details); playing with light projections and mirrors can showcase different aspects of the 3D prints and invite for playful exploration (we play not only with the image and the topography but also with the mirrored image of it);

3) Board Game

- **3 decks** of cards (*TIME* deck made of 8 blue cards; *CARE* deck made of 5 green cards and *DANGER* deck made of 5 red cards) and a **dashboard** (Fig. 8-9) have been designed and printed;
- The *Time cards* contain different images of the *Scream*, in different years, using different acquisition techniques (from B&W photography to HSI, RGB or 2D scan);
- The players will sit at the table close to the *Screen of the demonstrator* (where the tutorial and 2D scan are shown) and after they went through the whole sensorial experience on the 2D scan and 3D prints and visualized the tutorial, they are asked to create a chronological order (*Timeline*) of the *Scream* evolution since 1938 to the present.

Components of the game:

- 1 board (cardboard)
- 1 TIMELINE sheet
- 1 TIME CARDS deck (blue deck, 8 cards)
- 1 CARE CARDS deck (green deck, 5 cards)
- 1 DANGER CARDS deck (red deck, 5 cards)

Rules:

The game can be played by 2+ players. One will be the DANGER MASTER, the other(s) will team up as TIME TRAVELLER(S).

At the beginning of the game, the DANGER MASTER receives the DANGER CARDS (red deck), user manual and the TIMELINE sheet. He/She must be very careful of not showing the TIMELINE sheet to the TIME TRAVELLERS. The TIME TRAVELLERS receive the TIME CARDS (blue deck, shuffled) and the CARE CARDS (green deck).

The aim of the game is for the TIME TRAVELLERS to recreate a timeline of the *Scream*'s life, putting the TIME CARDS in order on the board, each card according to its date.

The DANGER MASTER is the only one to know the exact order in which the cards have to be positioned, shown on the TIMELINE sheet.

The DANGER MASTER can only play when the TIME TRAVELLERS make a mistake.

Any time the TIME TRAVELLERS make a mistake, the DANGER MASTER will play a DANGER CARD. To save the *Scream* from the danger, TIME TRAVELLERS have to choose the correct CARE CARD to counter-act on the DANGER CARD. If they pick the right CARE CARD, they can continue with their time journey and recreate the timeline of the *Scream*. You can find the correct combination of DANGER and CARE CARDS at the end of the user manual.

Be careful! If the DANGER MASTER plays all the DANGER CARDS before the TIME TRAVELLERS complete putting in the correct order the cards, they will lose the game. If they complete the timeline without making so many mistakes, they win.

TIMELINE SHEET

Figure 11: Timeline sheet cards. The images are taken from archival records as they are, without correction.

Figure 12: Danger and Care cards

PERCEIVE vocabulary (as part of the rules of the game, containing explanation of each Danger and Care card content)

Dangers:

1. **High Humidity:** is the main cause of fading for Cadmium yellow pigment in the Scream palette and can also cause swelling and other type of damages to cardboard and other moisture-sensitive paint materials
2. **Intense Light:** radiation in Visible and UV range can damage sensitive colours/pigments if too intense or exposed to it for prolonged periods (light-induced damage is cumulative)
3. **Surface Damage:** decay or degradation of the surface of the paint caused by mechanical agents or aggressive actions from the environment or during sudden events (robbery, vandalism etc.)
4. **Paint Loss:** loss and fading of a paint layers/materials due to different factors (aggression, abrasions, excessive exposure to low humidity and/or intense light that causes decohesion of paint and subsequent crumbling of the paint materials, etc.)
5. **Robbery:** a vandalic action where the art-object (painting) is stolen and removed from its place of display or storage

Care:

1. **Stabilize:** action meant to recover the stability of a paint/art-object if overexposed or underexposed to certain environmental parameters (light, relative humidity, pollution etc.)
2. **Monitor:** action meant to measure and keep under stable levels the environmental parameters (light, relative humidity, pollution etc.) that can potentially become damaging agents for a painting
3. **Control exposure:** action meant to control the levels of light exposure for exhibition/storage environments where fragile and sensitive art-objects are displayed
4. **Map:** action performed by a scientific equipment to identify and show the distribution of the materials present on a painted surface (this information can be further related to the technique of the artist and possible degradation or damage patterns on the surface)
5. **Reconstruct:** action aimed to build, re-establish, regenerate and/or simulate the appearance and colours of a painting surface if damaged or destroyed by external agents
6. **Consolidate:** action aiming to re-establish the cohesion between paint materials if there was a loss or degradation process affecting their integrity and stability
7. **Rejuvenate:** action meant to restore or revitalize the condition and characteristics of a painted surface (it can also mean reintegrate the paint colours if loss has happened and also simulate the original appearance and colours if fading or other type of colour change occurred over time)
8. **Recover:** action meant to recover a painting if stolen or lost due to several dangerous situations (robbery, vandalism, etc.)
9. **Exhibit:** action meant to showcase/display a painting in a protected, stable and friendly accessible environment.

Location

Blindern campus of University of Oslo during the workshop on 3rd June 2024 and InArt24 conference, and at the KHM museum in Oslo on 8th June 2024.

People involved in the design and demonstration sessions

Proof of concept and demonstration: Irina Sandu, Beatrice Boracchi, Sivert Thue, Aron Askeland (MUNCH); Emilien Leonhardt and Vincent Sabatier (HIROX Europe); Petros Stavroulakis, Panos Siozos (FORTH).

Evaluation team: Giorgio Trumpy, Irina Ciortan, Jon Yngve Hardeberg, Markus Storeide, Linda Favilini, Rebecca Franconi, Nina Eckerts (NTNU); Alfonsina Pagano (CNR).

Target group

- scientists, academics, students
- conservators, educators
- public (kids, teenagers, whole families)

Duration

After 15 min of experience (parts 1+2) and 15-20 min of board game, the total duration of the *Scream Time machine* experience would be 30-35 min.

Evaluation logistics

In this part few images of the demonstration run at the InArt24 pre-conference workshop on 3rd June and KHM museum, on 8th June are given to illustrate the whole experience and evaluation process.

Figure 13: First step of the evaluation questionnaire compilation

Figure 14: Participants watching the tutorial

Figure 15: 2D scan view

Figure 16: 3D print view

Figure 17: 2 attendees of the workshop playing the game under supervision of a Perceive fellow

Figure 18: Second step of evaluation, after the game was over

2.1.1.2 The Autochrome Viewer

The Autochrome Viewer demonstrator consists of two sides. One side illustrates to the user how the layering of coloured starch granules in the colour mosaic, when combined with the emulsion layer, contributes to the formation of a colour image. Although the layers of an actual autochrome are sandwiched together, these layers are separated in the Autochrome Demonstrator. These consist of the Emulsion layers and the Colour Mosaic layer. The layers contain image content of autochromes that was produced via multispectral image capture and advanced image processing, which is described in the PERCEIVE technical reports and some deliverables. The Emulsion layers presented on the Demonstrator contain the photographic emulsion. The Colour Mosaic Layer is always situated behind the emulsion layers and can be switched between the original mosaic and an unfaded one by physically substituting plate. The second side of the Autochrome Viewer demonstrator makes it possible to explore methods for "restoring" an Autochrome plate using AI. Here, the parts of the

emulsion that were either missing or damaged are reintroduced into the image, offering the viewer the experience of discerning between what was original and what was generated while being able to view the complete restored image. The missing emulsion is printed on a second emulsion layer, which is provided by AI processes.

The merge of the layer is to be observed from the viewing elements called “occulator” (Fig. 17).

Figure 19: The Autochrome Demonstrator exhibiting the layer structure of the colour image.

Figure 20: The Autochrome Demonstrator depicting the restoration effort. The occluders are the black elements at the extremities.

Location

Blindern campus of University of Oslo during the workshop on 3rd June 2024 and InArt24 conference, and at the KHM museum in Oslo on 8th June 2024.

People involved in the design and demonstration sessions

Proof of concept and demonstration: Arthur Clay and Chiara Fedon (HSLU), Irina Ciortan, Yoko Arteaga, Giorgio Trumpy (NTNU).

Evaluation team: Giorgio Trumpy, Irina Ciortan, Jon Yngve Hardeberg, Markus Storeide, Linda Favillini, Rebecca Franconi, Nina Eckerts (NTNU); Alfonsina Pagano (CNR).

Target group

- scientists, academics, students
- conservators, educators
- public (kids, teenagers, whole families)

Duration

2-5 minutes

Evaluation logistics

The experience with the Autochrome Viewer started with a description of the demonstrator and its elements from the creator.

Figure 21: The creator of presents the Autochrome Demonstrator

The user was then invited to have the experience independently. The experience consisted in walking around the table to see the layer structure and look through the *occulators* to see the layers merging in the complete visualization.

The evaluation consisted in the interview at the beginning, the observation during the experience, and the collection of feedback at the end of the experience.

2.2 Digital Heritage Expo, Archeovirtual and Manifattura Tabacchi (2025)

Manuele Veggi (CNR ISPC)

The Digital Heritage International Conference took place from 8th to 12th September 2025 in Siena. It is a premier international event that unites multiple heritage domains and conferences under one platform: covering fields such as computer science, cultural preservation, archaeology, art, and more, it brings together professionals from across domains. Besides the activities of the main conference, the event also hosts an *international expo*: the **Digital Heritage Expo** (<https://digitalheritage2025.unisi.it/expo/>). Open to the conference attendees, but also to external participants, including decision makers, professionals and citizens. It is a “scientific” exhibition, since exhibits are selected after a call and a peer review evaluation made by domain experts, scientists and artists. The expo is meant to offer a physical space where professionals, scientists and also citizens can meet, debate and be inspired by digital ideas applied to Cultural Heritage.

In the 2025 edition, PERCEIVE consortium participated actively in these events, not only presenting papers and poster to the main conference, but joining the EXPO with different installations:

- **PERCEIVE — Perceptions of Colour** by PERCEIVE Project; HSLU HSLU
- **PERCEIVE — Tools & Services** by PERCEIVE Project; CNR ISPC, FORTH, Fraunhofer IGD, NTNU, HSLU, IMKI MANN Museum, Munch Museum, V&M
- **PERCEIVE — *Perceive Isis’ Colours*** by PERCEIVE Project; CNR ISPC, MANN Museum

2.2.1 Description of *PERCEIVE Isis’ Colours*

Perceive Isis’ Colours is an interactive exhibition designed and set up by CNR ISPC and MANN in the framework of PERCEIVE Project (WP6). It groups together two different *prototypes* and is centred on the theme of the lost polychromy in the statues and frescoes decoration of the Temple of Isis in Pompeii (Scenario 1):

Echoes of Loss, a caring prototype

The exhibition developed around the caring prototype by CNR and MANN museum, was structured in three separate modules guiding visitors in discovery the loss, study and reconstruction of ancient polychromy, using the Venus Anadyomene as main case study. Its set-up foresees: an introductory video (*Echoes of Loss – The video*), an interactive tangible installation (*ColourLab*) and an interactive projection on a 3D printed replica of the statue (*Echoes of Colours*).

Figure 22: The three modules of PERCEIVE Isis’ Colours – Echoes of Loss (caring prototype)

The Gifts of Isis, an authenticity prototype

The Gifts of Isis is an interactive gamified experience created as a prototype aimed at enhancing tourists’ perceptions of authenticity in interactive museum experiences. It was developed following

the authenticity framework previously theorized at CNR. Authenticity is defined by three dimensions: the “Self” represents the user that interact with the experience; the “Other”, the social dimension that takes place when the user encounters other people and interact with them during the experience; and the “World”, the physical or digital environment where the experience is taking place. Each dimension includes specific components that play a role in shaping the perception of authenticity. The Gifts of Isis was originally designed as a multiplayer game, to integrate all three dimensions and their respective components and was later **evaluated to assess if their inclusion was effective in boosting visitor’s perception of authenticity**. The work is based on the authenticity framework developed within the project and published in Pescarin, Città, Spotti 2024, and in Pescarin et al 2025.

Figure 23: PERCEIVE Isis’ Colours – The Gifts of Isis (caring prototype)

In this context, the exhibition was awarded by the visitors the Digital Heritage Best Expo Prize. For a more detailed description of the two prototypes, please refer to Del. 6.1, together with Ch. 3 of PERCEIVE reference handbook *Chromatic Vision II* (Ciortan et al.; see also Del. 8.3), the catalogue of the exhibition (Barandoni et al.) and the corresponding page on PERCEIVE website (perceive-horizon.eu/index.php/results/perceive-isis-colours/).

2.2.1.1 Evaluations Follow-Ups of PERCEIVE Isis’ Colours

Beside the set-up at Digital Heritage Expo 2025, the exhibition was presented (totally or in part) in other venues over the past months.

- **Archeovirtual 2025 (Paestum, SA, Italy).** From 30th October to 2nd November 2025, *Echoes of Loss* was presented at ArcheoVirtual, the multimedia exhibition dedicated to digital applications and virtual archaeology projects in the framework of the Borsa Mediterranea del Turismo Archeologico in Paestum (SA), Italy (<http://www.archeovirtual.it>). The 2025 edition of the expo dealt the theme of “Digital Applications and Cultural Tourism” through a selection of innovative interactive applications and explanatory videos, selected through an international call for entries. The installations were open to heritage practitioners and citizens.
- **Set-up at ERIHS Central Hub (Florence, Italy).** After presenting the caring prototype in Paestum, the entire exhibitions *Perceive Isis’ Colours* was moved in its current set-up at central hub of the European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science (ERIHS, <https://www.e-rihs.eu/>). Here visits for prototypes are organised for scholars involved in scientific events (e.g. kick-off meeting of the Horizon Europe project COLOURS, <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101233413>) and for citizens. In Florence a single-user

version of the Gifts of Isis have been developed to test the importance of the social component on the perception of authenticity

3. UX Evaluation Results (*see also Del 7.1*)

3.1 Data collection and transcription

3.1.1 “InArt24” conference, Oslo

Alfonsina Pagano (CNR ISPC), Irina Ciortan (NTNU), Giorgio Trumpy (NTNU)

3.1.1.1 Location

The two prototypes were evaluated in two main locations: the Blindern campus (Georg Sverdrups Hus) of University of Oslo during the InArt workshop and conference, and afterwards at the Cultural History Museum (KHM) museum in Oslo. During the InArt conference, the Autochrome Viewer was displayed and evaluated in a quiet meeting room in the Blindern campus. At the same time, the Scream Time Machine demonstrator was displayed and evaluated in Auditorium 2 of Blindern Campus during the workshop and in the building’s lobby during the days of the conference.

On Saturday, after the conference, the demonstrators were moved to the museum environment, namely the Cultural History Museum, in the interactive “Kilden” room.

Table 1: Summary of PERCEIVE demonstrators, location of display and audience type.

Demonstrators	Pre-conference	Conference				Post-conference
		4th - TUE	5th - WED	6th - THU	7th - FRI	
	3rd - MON					8th - SAT
Scream Time Machine	Blindern Campus (Auditorium)	Blindern Campus (lobby)	Blindern Campus (lobby)	Blindern Campus (lobby)	Blindern Campus (lobby)	KHM
Autochrome Viewer	Blindern Campus – Undervisnings Room	KHM				
Audience	EXPERTS & PERCEIVE STAFF	Museum Visitors				

Figure 24: The location of the Autochrome Demonstrator throughout the conference

Figure 25: The two locations of the The Scream Time Machine demonstrator: Auditorium 2 (pre-conference workshop) and lobby outside Auditorium 1 (during conference days)

3.1.1.2 Collection

The “InArt” UX evaluation gathered data in these numbers, trying to match Target goals (see section 1.1.4):

Case study	OBS	QST
<i>Scream Time Machine</i>	38 users	39 users
<i>Autochrome Viewer</i>	23 users	27 users
	61 users observed	66 users questioned

PERCEIVE partners followed these steps:

- 1) Created and customized an online Form.
- 2) Distributed the form through a Tablet/iPad to users and collected responses.
- 3) Polished and checked data collected in shared Sheets.

- 4) Created charts in shared Sheets.
- 5) Exported the data and charts to an Excel file.
- 6) Read and (preliminary) analysed charts and graphs.
- 7) Analysed data making inferences, synthesis, pattern analysis and qualitative reads.

At the moment, we have done 1) to 6) steps. In the next months we will face stage 7). The PERCEIVE Analysis Framework indeed involves Four-levels:

First-Level Analysis [done in JUNE]:

- Follow the question-by-question structure of OBS and QST of both case studies.
- Read and thematically compare the responses' contents.
- Provide a summary of responses related to each found pattern.
- Logically (not deductively) compare quantitative data with the open-ended responses (qualitative ones).

Second-Level Analysis [To Do]:

- Disregard the original question order.
- Start comparing summaries across different patterns.
- Summarize points of convergence and divergence among the patterns.
- Include notable quotes.

Third-Level Analysis [To Do]:

- Establish correlations and inferences across various sections of OBS and QST, without adhering to the question order.
- Make deductions about individual themes emerging from the patterns.

Fourth-Level Analysis [To Do]:

- Reflect on the coincidences, divergences, deductions, and correlations to identify any relevant theories, models, or findings from previous research.
- If such references come to mind, briefly note them, including any citations and source

3.1.2 Digital Heritage, Archeovirtual and Manifattura Tabacchi (2025)

Manuele Veggi, Sofia Pescarin, Samuele Spotti (CNR ISPC), Valentina Bertelli (Univ. Of Bologna)

3.1.2.1 Location

Digital Heritage Expo took place at San Niccolò Palace (Via Roma 56, Siena, Italy), in the same premises of the main conference. As mentioned above, PERCEIVE Project consortium joined Digital Heritage Expo with three different booths, as depicted in the figure below.

Figure 26. Planimetry of Digital Heritage EXPO - PERCEIVE Projects booth are 5 (a, b) and 21 (a, b)

- PERCEIVE — Perceptions of Colour (booth 5a)
- PERCEIVE — Tools & Services (booth 5b)
- Perceive Isis’ Colours (booth 21a, *Echoes of Loss*, and 21b, *The Gifts of Isis*)

3.1.2.1.1 Following Set-Ups of *Perceive Isis’ Colours*

The **Archeovirtual Expo in Paestum** took place in the NEXT - New Exhibition Former SAIM Tobacco Factory, Cafasso Village (SA), Italy. A booth at the end of the exhibition area was dedicated to the set-up of *Echoes of Loss*. For a video recording of a guided visit of the caring prototype in this set-up, refer to the following article on the Italian national broadcasting service channel: RaiNews (*La riscoperta dei colori perduti del Tempio di Iside a Pompei, al BMTA 2025 di Paestum*, 30/10/2025, [link](#). Content available in Italian).

At the time writing, both prototypes are currently set-up at the main hall of **ERIHS Central Hub**, in Manifattura Tabacchi, via delle Cascine, 35, Florence. Guided visits to *Perceive Isis’ Colours* are organised by CNR ISPC team for citizens and practitioners (e.g. link to past visits open to citizens in December 2025, [link](#) for registration on EventBrite)

3.1.2.2 Collection

The **data collection protocol for *Perceive Isis’ Colours*** was handled separately for the two prototypes. The same protocol was adopted in the following setups of the exhibition in Paestum and Florence (open visit to the exhibition and COLOURS kick-off meeting, 1-5th December 2025).

Echoes of Loss.

The evaluation process consisted of two separates questionnaire, one before the experience (*pre-test*, QST-C1) and after the experience (*post-test*, QST-C2), transcribed in the Annexes of the current document. The evaluation process is aimed at: understanding the visitors’ appreciation and efficacy of the three different modules; assess visitors’ general appreciation of the prototype; verify whether visit to *Echoes of Loss* foster positive intentions towards cultural heritage (i.e. empirical validation of PERCEIVE Care Framework, see Veggi et al. 2026). We considered as valid participation to the questionnaire only if a visitors answered both QST-C1 and QST-C2. As a result, a sample of 70 participants was collected, as indicated in the following table.

Evaluation session	Participants QST-C1	Participants QST-C1 + C2
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Digital Heritage (Siena)	57	39
Archeovirtual (Paestum)	14	13
ERIHS Central Hub (Florence)	19	18
Total	90	70

The Gifts of Isis.

In both cases, the evaluation protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee of the National Research Council (Prot. CNR. n. 0526155), in line with the guidelines on human research of the Declaration of Helsinki (1964). All participants gave informed consent before completing the study. Participation was voluntary and without compensation. Future evaluations of the prototypes will focus on the measurement of cognitive and emotional responses of the visitors via biosensors devices (Biopac Research Ring), as described in Del. 6.1.

At DigitalHeritage 2025 and at Manifattura Tabacchi in Florence (Novembre 2025) we have carried out two assessments dedicated to the analysis of the perception of authenticity for the visitors on the exhibits. In order to assess if all components have the same weight in the perception of authenticity, we have carried out a comparative evaluation of the “Other” or social dimension. While the main application is **multiuser**, we have developed a second **single player version** to understand how removing one of the authenticity dimensions, specifically the “Other” dimension, would affect authenticity perception. The single and multiuser versions share the same physical setup and game mechanics, although the internal structure of the game was slightly modified to adapt the experience to being played by just one player.

Evaluation Protocol (multiuser version). When participants entered the exhibition room, they were welcomed by the operators, who explained how the experience worked and asked whether they agreed to take part. Participants were shown the three kiosks representing the three rewarding values and were encouraged to choose the one that they would like to receive as a gift from the goddess. Once they were ready, an operator would start the experience. Once it was completed, participants were asked to fill a questionnaire. All participants gave informed consent before completing the study. Participation was voluntary and without compensation. In the first part of the questionnaire, participants were asked the following personal information, including email address, age, city of origin, education level, occupation, in which extent their education or profession are related to cultural heritage or digital technologies, whether they ever visited the Iseum temple in Pompei, and whether they ever took part in an interactive experience related to cultural heritage. Data was later anonymized to guarantee privacy. The second part of the questionnaire followed the structure of the authenticity framework. Participants were presented with a series of statements, each related to a component of one the authenticity dimensions and were asked to express their level of agreement or disagreement, on a 5 point Lickert-scale (where 1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly disagree). The resulting

percentages showed whether single components were consistently perceived and if the overall experience was effective in conveying a sense of authenticity.

Participants:

- Total number of responses: 45 participants
- Age group: Adults aged between 25 and 58 years old
- Educational/professional background: highly educated (PhD: 51%, Master: 40%): 41 participants have jobs, while the remaining 4 are students. 28 participants claimed that their education or profession is highly related to cultural heritage.
- Previous visits to the Iseum Temple in Pompei: 71% of participants have never visited the temple.
- Previous participation in interactive experience related to cultural heritage: 80% of participants had tried at least once an interactive experience.

Evaluation Conditions:

- Quiet environment, the experience took place in a dedicated room.
- Operators present during all evaluations: 2, (Valentina Bertelli, Samuele Spotti)

Evaluation Protocol (single user version).

The evaluation protocol followed a similar structure to that of the multiplayer testing session. Participants were introduced to the experience by an operator and asked whether they agreed to take part. Participants took position in front of the kiosk, after which the operator started the experience. Once it was completed, participants were asked to fill a questionnaire. All participants gave informed consent before completing the study. Participation was voluntary and without compensation. The questionnaire used was the same that was employed for the previous testing session, with the

exception of one additional question asking participants whether they had previously tried the multiplayer version of the experience.

Participants:

- Total number of responses: 18 participants
- Age group: Adults aged between 26 and 38 years old
- Educational/professional background: highly educated (PhD: 33%, Master: 50%). 16 participants have a job, while the remaining 2 are students. 10 participants claimed that their education or profession is highly related to cultural heritage.
- Previous visits to the Iseum Temple in Pompei: 83% participants have never visited the temple.
- Previous participation in interactive experience related to cultural heritage: 83% of participants had tried an interactive experience before.
- Previous interactions with these exhibitions: only one of the participants had previously tried this experience before.

Evaluation Conditions:

- The environment in the exhibition space at ERIHS Central Hub in Florence was relatively quiet during open visits, while during COLOURS kick-off meeting the exhibition was mainly accessed during breaks when the room was crowded.
- Operators present during all evaluations: 1 (Valentina Bertelli)

3.2 Analysis of the evaluation data

3.2.1 The Scream Time Machine (2024-2025)

Participants:

- Total number of responses: 38 observed users + 39 questioned users
- Gender distribution: 40% male, 60% female
- Age group: Mainly adults (25-40 years old; 40-65 years old)

Evaluation Conditions:

- Locations quiet
- Operators present during all evaluations: 4 (Rebecca, Linda, Irina, Giorgio)

Key Findings:

1. *Understanding and Engagement*

- Participants were more interactive during the tactile experiences and asked numerous questions.
- Social interaction, such as discussions among participants and with organizers, enhanced engagement, though language differences occasionally posed a challenge.
- Some participants appeared bored or disengaged during longer explanations, indicating a need for more dynamic presentation methods.
- Many users found it challenging to understand the chronological ordering of the cards in the game, often struggling to differentiate between similar-looking images.
- Additional guidance or explanations were frequently required, highlighting the need for clearer instructions or visual aids.

2. *Comfort and Usability*

- Participants noted audio issues in the video, such as low volume or noise interference, suggesting a need for better sound quality management.
- The colours and details of the cards were sometimes perceived as inaccurate, impacting the overall experience and understanding.
- Visual aids, such as pointers or arrows, were suggested to help users focus on relevant parts of the presentation.

3. *Emotional Responses*

- The tactile experiences and high-resolution scans received positive feedback, with participants showing curiosity and excitement.
- Social and interactive elements of the game were highly engaging, with users finding the game fun despite the complexity.
- Technical expertise among some participants, such as knowledge of analogue photography, enhanced their engagement and understanding.

4. *Duration of Interaction*

- Interaction times is around 1 minute.

3.2.2 Autochrome Viewer (2024-2025)

Participants:

- Total number of responses: 23 observed users + 27 questioned users
- Gender distribution: 70% male, 20% female
- Age group: All adults (40-65 years old)

Evaluation Conditions:

- Locations varied from quiet to moderately crowded.
- Operators present during all evaluations: 3 (Markus, Irina, Giorgio)

Key Findings:

1. *Understanding and Engagement*

- Most users understood what they had to do, although one user needed some aid.
- Only w of them did not understand the task without help.
- Majority did not ask for help during the experience.
- Engagement was mixed, with some users passively participating and others actively participating.

2. *Comfort and Usability*

- Users generally found the movements required to interact with the installation comfortable and easy to accomplish.
- Some difficulties were noted with looking through the pinholes.
- Users' behaviour included looking through the Occulator and moving around the installation.

3. *Emotional Responses*

- Predominant emotions included curiosity and expectation.
- Some users experienced confusion, complexity, and disorientation.
- Positive emotions like excitement and relaxation were also noted.

4. *Duration of Interaction*

- Interaction times varied, with some users engaging for 2-5 minutes, and others interacting for less than 1 minute.

3.2.4 Evaluation results of the Caring Prototype: PERCEIVE Isis' Colours – Echoes of Loss (2025)

Manuele Veggi (CNR ISPC)

Participants:

- Total number of responses: 70 participants (QST-C1 + QST-C2, see §3.1.2.2)
- Gender distribution: 57% female; 42% men; 1% non-binary
- Age group: Adults (mainly aged between 30 and 40 years old, $M = 35.14$, range = 21 – 59 years old)
- Educational / professional background: highly educated (PhD: 42%, Master: 40%), 67% has job or is attending courses related / highly related to the heritage domain

Evaluation Conditions:

- Locations varied from crowded in the two expos to quiet / slightly crowded at ERIHS Central Hub
- Operators present during all evaluations: 1 (Manuele)

Key Findings:

1. *Assessment of the Single Modules*

1.1. *Module 1. Echoes of Loss (introductory video)*

1. Visitors feel anticipation, joy and trust, followed by surprise, as most relevant emotions. Their most relevant combinations (Plutchik dyads) are optimism, hope, and curiosity, which are aligned with the results on the *efficacy* (see later)
2. The concept of polychromy and the importance on care behaviour (paying attention to heritage sites / objects, historical empathy) are perceived as the most relevant
3. The video manages to reach both a cognitive and emotional involvement of the visitors on the concept of care

1.2. *Module 2. ColourLab*

1. The installation truly ignites a process of knowledge acquisition: a great majority of the participants understood the role of the different analysis techniques and the sequence of the phases of the colour reconstruction process

1.3. *Module 3. Echoes of Colours*

1. The installation is greatly appreciated by the visitors, who claimed to be positively engaged.

2. *Behavioural Change. Caring Intention and Perceived Efficacy*

1. Visiting *Echoes of Loss* has a positive impact on the intentions to carry out *caring actions*, in particular supporting research in the heritage fields and events / initiatives in this domain
2. Visiting *Echoes of Loss* has a positive impact on the perceived *individual efficacy* of the visitors: they become aware that their contribution is significant in taking care of cultural heritage

3. *General Appreciation and Conclusive Remarks*

1. *Echoes of Loss* puts at the centre the importance of interdisciplinary research in heritage science and of how visitors' individual attention and presence can contribute to cultural heritage preservation and valorisation
2. The caring prototype is effective and empirically validates PERCEIVE care framework

Main results visualisations are available in the Annex at the end of the deliverable.

3.2.5 Evaluation results of the Authenticity Prototype: PERCEIVE Isis' Colours – The Gifts of Isis (2025)

Valentina Bertelli (university of Bologna), Samuele Spotti (CNR ISPC)

We are listing here the key findings from the evaluation carried out in the multiuser and single user versions of the Gifts of Isis exhibition, designed around the Authenticity Prototype.

Multi-User Key Findings:

1. Self Dimension

1.1 Participants reported **high levels of curiosity and focus** (*I felt curious and engaged throughout the experience*: 47.1% Strongly agree, 51% Agree, 2% Strongly Disagree).

1.2 **Choices were perceived as meaningful and the experience met personal expectations** (80% of users agreed or strongly agreed with the statement: *I was offered meaningful choices and challenges*). Users were asked to choose the kiosk representing the value that they would like to obtain from the goddess, so they were trying to achieve something that resonated with them.

1.3 All participants agreed that the experience was **immersive and rich**.

2. Other dimension

2.1 90% of users agreed or strongly agreed on **being able to exchange perspectives with others, indicating that the experience favours dialogue**.

2.2 In the majority of cases, participants agreed on **being able to perceive social practices, norms and embodiment**.

2.3 Larger part of the participants **disagreed or felt neutral towards the occurrence of unexpected interactions** (Unplanned or surprising social interactions occurred: 11.8% Strongly agree, 35.3% Agree, 29.4% Neither agree nor disagree, 13.7% Disagree, 9.8% Strongly disagree).

3. World Dimension

3.1 The environment was largely **perceived as credible and realistic and historical information was reputed trustworthy**.

3.2 The **atmosphere** of the experience was positively received by the majority of participants.

3.3 **Time flow was the “World” dimension’s component that drew more neutrality and disagreements** (21.6% Neither agree nor disagree, 23.5% Disagree).

Single-User Key Findings:

1. Self Dimension

1.1. **Some users struggled with remaining engaged and focussed during the entire experience** (*I felt curious and engaged throughout the experience*: 11.1% Neither agree nor disagree; 5.6 % Disagree; *I was able to stay focused and mentally present*: 22.2% Neither agree nor disagree; 11.1% Disagree). The single player version takes significantly more time to complete, as the user is required to play all roles. This may explain why users felt less engaged and struggled with maintaining focus throughout the experience. The amount of text and information provided is also higher compared to the multiplayer version.

1.2. **Percentages of disagreement towards meaningfulness of choices and match of expectations were significantly higher** (*I was offered meaningful choices and challenges*: Disagree: 16.7%; *The experience met my expectations and had personal relevance*: Disagree: 11.1%). A possible explanation could be the fact that choosing and obtaining all gifts may reduce their perceived significance, making them feel less distinctive or meaningful. Covering more roles may also result in a less tailored experience for each character.

1.3. **Emotions and embodiment scored higher percentages of neutrality and disagreement**. Ex. *I experienced emotions during the experience (e.g., awe, sadness, joy)*: 38.9% Neither agree nor disagree, 16.7% Disagree; *I felt mentally or physically “inside” the experience*: 27.8% Neither agree nor disagree, 16.7% Disagree.

2. Other Dimension

2.1 **Disagreement and neutrality towards the perception of language exchange, collaboration, social practices and social unpredictability** are significantly higher.

2.2 Overall, the **social dimension scored significantly lower** values than the multiplayer version, even though percentages of agreements were never completely absent. Some of the evaluations of this version took place during the breaks of a conference, in an *environment that was often crowded and noisy*, rather than in a quiet and separate room as in the multiplayer version. As a result, players occasionally engaged in conversations or interacted with other people nearby while still playing alone, which may have enhanced social perception.

3. World Dimension

3.1 **Users agreed on the environment's credibility and atmosphere** supporting the experience.

3.2 **50% of participants felt neutral towards environmental unpredictability.**

3.3 **Environmental embodiment as less perceived in this version** (*The environment responded to my actions in a tangible way*: 22.2% Neither agree nor disagree, 22.2% Disagree)

Conclusions.

The experience that proved to be perceived as more authentic was the multiplayer version, which integrates all the dimensions of authenticity and their respective components. In the multiplayer condition, the **“Self” dimension** received high levels of agreement across most components, with most participants agreeing or strongly agreeing with the perception of its components [**Personal disposition, personal context, cognition, perception**]. The experience was perceived as immersive, meaningful, engaging, and prompted reflection. Regarding the **“Other” dimension**, participants generally agreed on their ability to perceive **language exchange, social practices, and social norms**. The variable that showed the highest levels of disagreement was **social unpredictability**. This may depend on the type of participants involved: in some cases, players already knew each other, which may have reduced the level of surprise in social interactions. Nevertheless, this lack seems not to be fundamental in the general perception of authenticity. Alternatively, it may simply indicate a calm and predictable flow of the experience. The **“World” dimension** obtained positive results, showing that participants generally agreed on the credibility and coherence of the environment [**Physical context**], the reliability of the historical information [**Verification**], and the quality of the **atmosphere**.

In the single-player version, **the “Self” dimension** showed notable percentages of neutrality and disagreement in components such as meaningfulness [**Personal context**], curiosity [**Personal disposition**], **embodiment**, and **emotional engagement**, showing how also the general perception of authenticity has been impacted. This may also be related to the structure of the experience, which required more time to complete and greater cognitive effort due to the increased amount of text and information to process. Since the single player version was modelled after the multiplayer experience to ensure comparability, the increased duration and large information load were unavoidable, as a single user is required to complete all tasks that were originally planned for three participants. Therefore, this bias could not be reduced without significant redesign of the structure of the single player version. In addition, being required to choose and obtain all values may have reduced their perceived distinctiveness and personal relevance for individual users. **The “Other” dimension** was the one that showed the greatest difference, obviously, between the two versions, since the single-player version was specifically designed to investigate differences in authenticity perception when the social dimension was removed. Although the “Other” dimension recorded higher percentages of neutrality and disagreement in this version, agreement towards the perception of its components was not absent in the results [**Language exchange, social norms**]. This may suggest that, even when an experience is designed for a single player, the presence of other people in the surrounding environment may still contribute to the construction of a sense of community (although this is an assumption that would need further analysis). **The “World” dimension obtained similar results to the multiplayer version**, indicating the effectiveness of the setup for single play use. Participants agreed on historical accuracy [**Verification**], realism of the **physical context** and immersive

atmosphere, while **environmental embodiment** and **unpredictability** scored notable percentages of neutrality and disagreement.

3.3 Analysis of learning-based and classical approaches

In this section, we explain our choice of approach through a qualitative comparison of learning-based and classical methods. The detailed selection process is covered in Work Package 4 (Deliverable 4.1: Training Data and Image-Based Rendering Techniques). Here, we summarize the key points for better clarity.

Colour reconstruction of Lenticular films

The original reconstruction pipeline using signal processing effectively reconstructed most lenticular scans. However, it struggled with films where the lenticular lines were not perfectly straight. Learning-based approaches using deep learning addressed these limitations by taking a different approach, leveraging data from signal processing as ground truths for plausible reconstructions. They also incorporated data augmentation and fine-tuning based on user guidance to enhance the results. This made learning-based methods more effective than classical approaches for solving this problem.

Neural restoration of greening defects in digitized autochromes

Autochromes are fragile and prone to various defects, one of which is greening. These defects are difficult to restore using traditional signal processing methods or even advanced photo editing tools like Photoshop. To address this, we explored how learning-based approaches compare to classical methods. We successfully used synthetic data generation from deep learning to simulate greening defects on clean autochrome photographs. By training our model on this synthetic data, we achieved plausible results that can be further refined using both AI and non-AI techniques to meet specific needs.

3D digitization and colour reconstruction of CH objects

State-of-the-art learning-based methods like Neural Radiance Fields (NeRF) and Gaussian Splatting (GS) can render photorealistic scenes from just a few multi-view images. In contrast, traditional methods require more time and perform better in controlled environments, particularly for inferring geometry and material characteristics. In the field of cultural heritage, precise reconstruction of geometry is very important. However, traditional approaches struggle with segmentation of 3D and 2D images. To leverage the strengths of both, we used traditional methods for geometry and material capture in controlled settings and employed learning-based techniques to segment regions of interest, such as areas with traces of pigments. More details on this approach can be found in Deliverable 4.1, covering the scenarios of Polychromy (statue) and Textiles.

4. Comments on UX results

(see also Del 7.1, Chapter 4.3.4)

All involved partners

In our first UX evaluation session at “InArt” conference, in Oslo, about the two demonstrators “The Scream Time Machine” and “Autochrome Viewer”, we identified some key areas for improvement and success factors:

1. **Knowledge transfer** about:
 - Lost polychromy

- Colour changes through time
 - Various coloured versions of the artwork
 - Autochrome film technique
 - Difference between original and restored copies
 - Integrations of the conservative process
2. **Overall experience** of the demonstrators, the usage phases and the interactive modes
 3. **UX evaluation process** (method, protocol, logistics, duration, operators...)

It is relevant to highlight how this stage is preliminary to more in-depth analysis which will follow in the next months.

In general, both demonstrators received highly positive impact. Despite some issues, most participants particularly enjoyed discovering what an autochrome is and visualizing the original autochromes. This positive response indicates that the content itself is highly engaging and intriguing to users. It suggests that with the right guidance and information, the Autochrome Viewer can captivate and educate its audience effectively. Leveraging this interest by enhancing the content and presentation could further improve user satisfaction.

Whereas the “Scream Time Machine” game was praised for its high entertainment value, largely due to the social interaction it fosters, and the various roles players can assume. These aspects encourage collaboration and competition, making the learning process more engaging and enjoyable. Enhancing these social elements and possibly expanding the roles or tasks could further boost the game's appeal and educational impact.

4.1 Knowledge transfer (1)

4.1.1 The Scream Time Machine

1. *Change the Current Cards with Corrected Restored Images of the Colour Films.* Updating the current cards to include corrected and restored images of the colour films will enhance the visual accuracy and historical fidelity of the game. Restored images provide a clearer and more engaging representation, helping users better understand and appreciate the historical context. This improvement will also make the game more visually appealing, potentially increasing user satisfaction and engagement.

2. *Use Corrected Images of The Scream for Chronological Re-ordering.* In future versions, utilizing corrected images of “The Scream>” will help users more accurately re-order the events chronologically in the board game. Accurate images will provide clearer visual clues, aiding users in understanding the timeline and improving their overall experience. This change can make the educational aspect of the game more effective by providing a more intuitive understanding of the historical sequence.

4.1.2 Autochrome Viewer

1. *Improve Colour Accuracy of the Printing.* Enhancing the colour accuracy of the printed autochromes is essential for an authentic and visually pleasing user experience. Accurate colour reproduction ensures that the autochromes are seen as they were originally intended, preserving their historical and artistic value. This improvement can significantly enhance the educational impact and aesthetic enjoyment for users.

2. *Finetune the Geometrical Alignment by Mounting the Elements on Rails.* Finetuning the geometrical alignment by mounting the elements on rails will ensure precise positioning and stability. Proper alignment is crucial for accurately viewing the autochromes, as misalignments can distort the image and reduce the clarity and effectiveness of the display. Rails provide a reliable mechanism to maintain alignment, enhancing the overall user experience.

3. *Regulate the Transparency of the Layers to Achieve an Effective Overlay.* Regulating the transparency of the layers is vital for achieving an effective visual overlay. Proper transparency allows users to see multiple layers of information clearly, enhancing their understanding of the autochrome's composition and historical context. This adjustment can make the viewing experience more informative and engaging.

4. *Remove the Blue Colour Bias of the Lightbox.* Eliminating the blue colour bias of the lightbox will ensure that the colours of the autochromes are displayed accurately. A colour-neutral light source is essential for true-to-life colour representation, allowing users to see the autochromes as they were intended. This correction can significantly improve the visual quality and authenticity of the display.

5. *Choose an Autochrome Sample with More Vivid Colours.* Selecting autochrome samples with more vivid colours, such as a flower bouquet, will make the display more visually striking and engaging. Vivid colours can capture users' attention and make the viewing experience more enjoyable and memorable. This choice can also enhance the educational impact by showcasing the potential of autochrome technology in capturing vibrant, lifelike images.

6. *Having Two Colour Mosaic Layers.* Introducing two colour mosaic layers, allowing users to switch between the original faded state and a digitally unfaded version, will provide a dynamic and educational experience. This feature enables users to understand the aging process of autochromes and appreciate the restoration efforts. It adds an interactive element, making the display more engaging and informative.

By addressing these aspects, both “The Scream Time Machine” and the “Autochrome Viewer” can offer more accurate, engaging, and educational experiences, enhancing user satisfaction and the overall effectiveness of the demonstrations.

4.2 Overall experience (2)

4.2.1 The Scream Time Machine

1. *Complexity of Chronological Ordering.* The primary challenge identified in "The Scream Time Machine" was the complexity of the chronological ordering of the game cards. Many users struggled to arrange the cards in the correct sequence, which detracted from their overall experience. This complexity could stem from the nuanced historical details or insufficient contextual clues provided on the cards. Simplifying the task or offering more guidance could help users engage more effectively with the educational content of the game.

2. *Added Value of Backlighting.* The feature of shining a white light behind the 2D prints did not resonate with many users, who did not perceive it as adding significant value to their experience. This might be because the backlighting did not enhance the visual quality or comprehension of the prints in a meaningful way. Re-evaluating this feature and considering alternative enhancements, such as interactive elements or augmented reality overlays, could provide a more impactful user experience.

3. *Subtitles for Audio-Impaired Users.* Adding subtitles to the video tutorial is crucial for inclusivity. This adjustment would ensure that audio-impaired users can fully understand and engage with the tutorial content. Subtitles also benefit non-native speakers and those in noisy environments, making the game more accessible to a broader audience.

4. *Success of High-Resolution Scan Exploration.* The exploration of the high-resolution scan was a standout success. Users appreciated the ability to examine detailed images closely, which likely provided a deeper understanding and appreciation of “The Scream”. This positive feedback suggests that incorporating more high-resolution scans or interactive elements allowing users to explore artwork in detail could enhance educational outcomes and user satisfaction.

By addressing these points, “The Scream Time Machine” can be refined to better meet user needs and expectations, ultimately making it a more effective and enjoyable educational tool.

4.2.2 Autochrome Viewer

1. *Add Pointer/Arrow: “Look Here”*. Users (but also operators) suggested adding a pointer or arrow with the instruction “Look here” to guide them on where to focus their attention within the Autochrome Viewer. This is important because users can feel overwhelmed or uncertain about where to look, especially when presented with complex visual information. A clear indicator can streamline the user experience, reducing confusion and ensuring that users fully engage with the key elements of the display.

2. *Add More Explanations on What is an Autochrome*. The need for additional explanations about what an autochrome is, was highlighted. Many users are likely unfamiliar with autochromes, an early colour photography process. Providing background information, historical context, and technical details can enrich the user experience, making the interaction more educational and engaging. Enhanced understanding leads to greater appreciation and curiosity, which are crucial for cultural and historical exhibitions.

3. *Fix the Position of the Occulator to Avoid Misalignments*. Users (and operators) noted the importance of properly fixing the position of the occulator to prevent misalignments. Misalignment can significantly detract from the viewing experience, making it difficult to properly see and appreciate the autochromes. Ensuring precise alignment is crucial for maintaining image clarity and ensuring that users can accurately view the details of the autochromes without unnecessary frustration or discomfort.

4. *Confusion Regarding Mimetic or Discernible Inpainting Effect*. One user expressed confusion about whether the goal was to achieve a mimetic (realistic) inpainting effect or a discernible (visible) one. This feedback highlights the need for clarity in the presentation of restoration techniques and objectives. Clearly communicating the intent and method behind the inpainting can help users understand and appreciate the artistic and technical decisions involved in the restoration process. Providing side-by-side comparisons or detailed explanations could resolve this confusion and enhance the educational value.

By addressing these aspects, the Autochrome Viewer can become more user-friendly and educational, providing a richer and more satisfying experience for all users.

4.3 UX Evaluation Process (3)

We also did self-reflection on the evaluation methodology and protocol. What emerged is:

1. *Remove Redundant Questions*. It is essential to eliminate redundant questions within the questionnaire to streamline the evaluation process. Repeated questions can frustrate participants and lead to inconsistent or disengaged responses. Ensuring each question is unique and purposeful will enhance the quality of the data collected and improve the overall user experience. However, the same evaluation method suggested repeated questions to make clear what operators collected from users. Sometimes same concept proposed in different manner led to different answers.

2. *Better Crafting of the Questions*. Improving the crafting of questions is vital to obtaining clear, accurate, and meaningful responses. Well-designed questions that are concise, clear, and directly related to the evaluation objectives will help participants provide more precise and valuable feedback. This refinement ensures that the data collected is both relevant and insightful. Evaluation templates undergone linguistic supervision and psychological survey by CNR experts. However, this phase has been done in a short time before InArt conference. It might need more time for revision.

3. *Optimize Typology and Number of Questions.* Optimizing the type and number of questions is necessary to maintain participant engagement and gather comprehensive data. An excessive number of questions or poorly chosen question types can overwhelm users, resulting in lower-quality responses. Balancing the number and type of questions ensures that the evaluation is thorough without being burdensome.
4. *Add Drop-Down List for Known Apriori Details.* Incorporating drop-down lists for known details such as location and the names of operators can significantly improve the speed and accuracy of completing the questionnaires. This approach reduces the risk of errors in data entry and ensures that all responses are standardized, facilitating easier analysis and interpretation.
5. *Make a Unique Form Connecting All Three Stages of Evaluation.* Creating a single form that connects the pre-experience, observation, and post-experience stages will help avoid errors associated with typing user codes between different forms. This unified approach ensures consistency in data collection and reduces the administrative burden on both participants and evaluators.
6. *Technical Issues on the submission phase.* Addressing and mitigating technical issues that can be avoided is crucial for a smooth evaluation process. Technical glitches can disrupt the user experience, lead to incomplete data, and frustrate participants. Proactively identifying potential technical problems with device and support used for the evaluation will ensure a seamless evaluation experience and reliable data collection. Wifi connectivity for tablet can be an issue when collecting users' feedback.
7. *Separate Roles of Demonstrator Creator and Experience Moderator.* The demonstrator's author should not act as the experience moderator to avoid any potential bias or influence on the evaluation results. Introducing a dedicated experience's moderator ensures that the demonstrator is explained and guided without any interference, leading to more objective and reliable user feedback.
8. *Consistency of Details Offered to the User.* Maintaining consistency in the information provided to users is crucial for a fair and effective evaluation. Writing a script with standardized instructions for the experience moderator to present ensures that all participants receive the same information, reducing variability in the user experience and improving the reliability of the data collected. This has been planned for InArt conference, providing a sort of script. Nevertheless, since different operators conducted the evaluations not all followed the instructions.

By addressing these methodological aspects, the evaluation process can be significantly improved in the future PERCEIVE sessions, resulting in higher-quality data and a better understanding of the user experience.

5. Metrological evaluation

Colour accuracy in video mapping - Perceive Isis' Colours

The statue of *Venus Anadyomene* from the Iseum of Pompeii was included in a prototype developed within the PERCEIVE project. The 3D model obtained through the photogrammetry acquisition described in Section 2.1.3 of Deliverable 3.3 was used to produce a 3D-printed replica of the statue. The print, realised in white plastic, was featured in the exhibition "*Perceive Isis' Colours*", described in detail in Deliverable 8.3. Video-mapping techniques were applied to the printed replica to visualise the statue's original colours, reconstructed on the basis of the mock-ups presented in Section 2.1 of Deliverable 3.2, which provide information on the lost polychromy. Based on the spatially varying bidirectional reflectance distribution function (SVBRDF) measurements of these mock-ups, a computer-generated image representing a plausible appearance of *Venus Anadyomene* was produced using computer graphics techniques (Fig. 27, left).

Fig. 27 – Possible chromatic palette reconstruction of *Venus Anadyomene* (left) and preliminary exhibit setup of “*Perceive Isis’ Colours*”, including the 3D-printed copy of the statue (right).

The experience offered to visitors in “*Perceive Isis’ Colours*” included the projection of the reconstructed appearance onto the 3D-printed statue. The projector was concealed from the observer, and the projected light was intended to create the impression of intrinsic material colour on the statue’s surface. However, simply projecting the target image can lead to deviations in the perceived appearance due to variations in surface reflectance across different points and orientations. Such deviations may compromise both the realism and the effectiveness of the experience.

In this augmented reality (AR) setting, the statue is illuminated by two distinct sources: a predominantly diffuse ambient light originating from multiple directions, and a highly directional light emitted by the projector and focused on the object’s surface. For a given viewing position V , two reflectance images are required:

- (I) the reflectance image corresponding to the illumination angle of the projected light and the collection angle associated with the viewing position ($R^{\%}_{\text{proj-V}}$);
- (II) the reflectance image corresponding to diffuse ambient illumination and the same collection angle ($R^{\%}_{\text{full-V}}$).

The total spectral radiance reflected by the surface under combined illumination (ambient light + projector) is given by:

$$S_{\text{room+proj}} = (IRR_{\text{room}} * R^{\%}_{\text{full-V}}) + (IRR_{\text{proj}} * R^{\%}_{\text{proj-V}})$$

where IRR_{room} and IRR_{proj} denote the irradiances provided by the ambient illumination and the projector, respectively.

In an ideal scenario, the projected image would be computed by accounting for the specific reflective properties of each surface point, ensuring that the intended appearance is accurately reproduced. In the case of “*Perceive Isis’ Colours*”, direct projection of the target image was considered acceptable because the 3D-printed statue was made of white plastic. Nevertheless, the surface reflectance deviates from ideal Lambertian behaviour, leading to variations in reflectivity depending on local surface orientation.

This section reports an assessment of the deviations from the intended appearance resulting from direct projection without compensation. These results form the basis for future improvements involving compensation strategies that account for the reflective characteristics of the projection surface. Such compensation will be particularly critical when projecting onto original artworks or heterogeneous materials rather than uniform white replicas.

Spectroradiometric measurements were conducted on the 3D-printed statue within the projection-based AR setup of “*Perceive Isis’ Colours*”. The collection angle was aligned with a typical observer’s viewing direction, as illustrated in Fig. 1 (right). For each measurement point, four conditions were recorded: (1) projection of the white point, (2) projection of the black point, (3) projection of the intended colour, and (4) ambient illumination only (no projection). These measurements were used to compute the perceived colour values and compare them with the intended colours defined by the RGB values of the projected image.

Measurements were taken at nine locations: three on the yellow hair, three on the white body, and three on the red garment, as indicated by the red markers in Fig. 28 (left).

From the measured spectral radiances, tristimulus values were calculated using the CIE 1931 2° Standard Observer. The resulting chromaticity values were plotted in the CIE 1976 UCS diagram (Fig. 28, right). As the colours are relatively low in saturation, the data points cluster within a small central region of the diagram. An enlarged inset highlights the presence of three distinct clusters corresponding to the different colour areas.

In the described AR context, the goal is to deceive the observer’s visual system by concealing the projector, such that the structured projected light is perceived as an intrinsic reflective property of the object under environmental illumination. The CIELAB colour space is well suited for quantifying the perceived colour of reflective objects, as it incorporates mechanisms for discounting the illuminant and accounting for contextual appearance. Accordingly, deviations from the intended appearance—defined by the projected image—were evaluated in CIELAB space.

Fig. 28 – Measurement points for the spectroradiometric captures (left) and corresponding chromaticity values plotted in the CIE 1976 UCS diagram (right).

The spectroradiometric measurement of the projector’s white point reflected from the statue was used as the reference white for the CIELAB calculations. Reference values were derived from the RGB pixel values of the projected image, assuming the BT.709 colour space.

Fig. 29 – Tridimensional colourimetric values plotted in the CIELAB space: a^*-b^* , L^*-a^* , and L^*-b^* projections.

The three-dimensional colourimetric data were plotted in the a^*-b^* , L^*-a^* , and L^*-b^* projections of the CIELAB space (Fig. 29). Comparison between the reference colours from the projected image and the measured values in the AR setting reveals a systematic increase in lightness (L^*) and a pronounced shift toward lower a^* values. This trend is consistent across all measured regions of the statue.

These results indicate that, even in the simplified case of a white 3D-printed statue—where direct projection might be assumed sufficient—the lack of compensation for surface reflectance leads to noticeable colour deviations. Implementing a compensation image that counterbalances the material’s reflective properties, and their spatial variability would have resulted in a more faithful reproduction of the intended colours.

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Annex 1 – Scream Time Machine templates

Questionnaire

ONLY 4 AUDIENCE

QUEST # Scream Time Machine (MUNCH)

Questionnaire ID:_____ Operator:_____ Location: _____ Date:___/___/_____

[PERCEIVE staff member] Hi, my name is _____ and I am a staff member of PERCEIVE PROJECT, which is conducting visitors studies on this occasion. We would like to know what you think of the demonstrator/tool/service/demo. In other words, what you like and don't like, what works and what needs to be improved for the near future.

We are not evaluating you, but the product itself. The questionnaire is anonymous.

For this reason I would like to ask you for 6-7 minutes to participate in our survey.

It would be a great help to us!

Firstly, I will ask you a series of questions aimed to understand your profile; and then, I will ask you to experience what you have in front of you (*video tutorial + tactile exploration + game card*); then some specific questions about your personal opinions to close the survey.

If you have any questions before you start, you can ask without any problem.

#Demographics (General questions for profiling the user)

1.1. City/Country of origin: _____

1.2. Gender:

- Male
- Female
- Not declared

1.3. Age group:

- 0-25
- 25-40
- 40-65
- 65+

1.4. Area of employment:

- Unoccupied
- Culture
- Agriculture/Environment
- Computing
- Social/Training
- Student
- Engineering/Architecture
- ICT/Communication
- Other: _____

1.5. Do you have any sight issues?

- Yes
- No

#Pre-experience (Preliminary questions to identify user preferences)

2.1. How many times do you visit a cultural site or a museum during the year?

- None

- 1-2 times per year
- 3-5 times per year
- 5+ times per year

2.2. In a cultural site or museum, which type of visit support would you like to use? *(select one or more than one answer)*

- No support, I prefer a free visit
- A guided tour with a physical person
- A paper-based guide
- An audio-guide
- An application on a mobile phone or tablet
- An application on a touch totem or PC
- A digital touchable replica or 3D prints
- Something to play with

2.3. How do you prefer to receive information in a cultural site or museum? *(select one or more than one answer)*

- Reading panels with texts and images by myself
- Listening to a guide's narration
- Watching a video
- Using a multimedia installation
- Playing games

2.4. Have you ever seen the Munch's Scream in person?

- Yes
- No

2.5. What do you know about the Munch's Scream?

- Nothing
- I heard about _____ *(please write here)*

(20 min.)
#Time For Experience + Playing With Cards

#Post-experience *(Questions related to the user's considerations after experiencing the product)*

3.1. How much did you enjoy the experience of "Scream Time Machine"?

(put an X on the degree of preference)

1 (Not at all) 2 3 4 5 (Very much)

3.2. What is the aspect you liked most out of this experience? *(select one or more than one answer)*

- The video at the beginning of the experience
- The high-res scan of the Scream
- The card game
- The 3D printed replicas

3.3. Why? *(select one or more than one answer)*

- The story told
- Colors
- Hands-on activity

- Touchable 3D replicas
- The innovative way of explaining an artwork
- (please write here extra comments done by user)_____

3.4. How much did you like the TACTILE EXPLORATION of the Scream? (put an X on the degree of preference)

1 (Not at all) 2 3 4 5 (Very much)

3.5. What type of sensations did the TACTILE EXPLORATION allow you to feel? (select one or more than one answer)

- Curiosity
- Wonder
- Complexity
- Excitement
- Confusion
- Disorientation
- Expectation
- Pleasure
- Relax
- Disturb
- Boredom
- More: _____(please write here extra comments from user)

3.6. How does the projection of light behind the 3D TACTILE REPLICAS affect you? (put an X on the degree of preference)

1 (Disturbing) 2 3 4 5 (Pleasant)

3.7. And what about the VIDEO TUTORIAL: how would you consider the duration? (put an X on the degree of preference)

1 (Not appropriate) 2 3 4 5 (Appropriate)

3.8. Is the language used in the VIDEO TUTORIAL easy to understand?

- Yes
- No, why?: _____(please write here)

3.9. Let's play together! Are you able to retrace how many original Scream images you saw in the VIDEO TUTORIAL AND CARD GAME? (select one or more images)

3.10. Try to associate a sentiment to the following images of the Munch's Scream, you saw in the VIDEO TUTORIAL.

(please write here)

(please write here)

3.11. How do you consider the CARD GAME? *(put an X on the degree of preference)*

USEFULNESS FOR UNDERSTANDING THE SCREAM INFOS

1 (Not useful at all) 2 3 4 5 (Extremely useful)

USABILITY OF THE GAME MECHANISMS TO GET MORE INFOS ON THE SCREAM

1 (Complex to play with) 2 3 4 5 (Extremely easy to play)

DURATION OF THE GAME

1 (Not appropriate) 2 3 4 5 (Appropriate)

3.12. Which moment of the CARD GAME do you enjoy the most?

----- *(please write here)*

3.13. Which moment of the CARD GAME you didn't enjoy?

----- *(please write here)*

3.14. By the end, which are the main insights you got from the "Scream Time Machine" experience?

(select one or more than one answer)

- Understand color changes through time
- Different versions of the artwork
- Different type of documentation of the artwork
- Different analyses and studies on the artwork
- Extra note: ----- *(please write here)*

[PERCEIVE staff member]

Thank you for your time and cooperation!

Your feedback is precious and will help us in our research.

Observation

ONLY 4 PERCEIVE MEMBER STAFF

OBS # Scream Time Machine (MUNCH)

# Observation			
Questionnaire ID:_____ Operator:_____ Location: _____ Date:___/___/_____			
0.1. Gender: <input type="checkbox"/> Male <input type="checkbox"/> Female <input type="checkbox"/> Not expressed <input type="checkbox"/> _____	0.2. Age group: <input type="checkbox"/> Child <input type="checkbox"/> Teenager <input type="checkbox"/> Adult <input type="checkbox"/> Retired	0.3. Location condition: <input type="checkbox"/> Quiet <input type="checkbox"/> Confusing <input type="checkbox"/> Crowded but still quiet <input type="checkbox"/> _____	
VIDEO-TUTORIAL			
0.4. Does the user see the video? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No, <i>why?</i> : _____ <i>(please write here)</i>			
0.5. Does the user watch it till the end? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No, <i>why?</i> : _____ <i>(please write here)</i>			
0.6. Does the user seem to care about the video or is it distracted? <input type="checkbox"/> Interested to the video <input type="checkbox"/> Not caring at the video			
0.7. Does the user talk while he/she watches it? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, with whom? _____ what does he/she say? _____ <input type="checkbox"/> No			
CARD GAME			
0.8. How many participants are playing? <input type="checkbox"/> 2 persons <input type="checkbox"/> 3 persons <input type="checkbox"/> 4 persons <input type="checkbox"/> More than 4 persons			
0.9. Does the user know the other participants of the game? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No			
0.10. Is the user in silence or comment aloud/ talk with others? <input type="checkbox"/> Silence <input type="checkbox"/> Talk			
0.11. Does the user seem to understand what he/she has to do?			

Yes, *why?*: _____ (please write here)

No, *why?*: _____ (please write here)

0.12. Does the user seem comfortable in doing this activity?

Yes, *why?*: _____ (please write here)

No, *why?*: _____ (please write here)

0.13. What type of emotions does the user seem to feel?

Curiosity

Wonder

Complexity

Excitement

Confusion

Disorientation

Expectation

Pleasure

Relax

Disturb

Boredom

Other: _____

TACTILE EXPLORATION

0.14. Does the user seem involved in touching the surface?

Yes, *why?*: _____ (please write here)

No, *why?*: _____ (please write here)

0.15. Is the user in silence or comment aloud/ talk with others?

Silence

Talk

0.16. How long does the user do this activity?

Less than 30 seconds

30 sec- 60 sec.

More than 60 seconds

Extra comments from Operator:

Annex 2 – Autochrome Viewer templates

Questionnaire

ONLY 4 AUDIENCE

QUEST # Autochrome Viewer (HLSU)

Questionnaire ID:_____ Operator:_____ Location: _____ Date:___/___/_____

[PERCEIVE staff member] Hi, my name is _____ and I am a staff member of PERCEIVE PROJECT, which is conducting visitors studies on this occasion. We would like to know what you think of the demonstrator/tool/service/demo. In other words, what you like and don't like, what works and what needs to be improved for the near future.

We are not evaluating you, but the product itself. The questionnaire is anonymous.

For this reason I would like to ask you for 6-7 minutes to participate in our survey.

It would be a great help to us!

Firstly, I will ask you a series of questions aimed to understand your profile; and then, I will ask you to experience what you have in front of you (**autochrome**); then some specific questions about your personal opinions to close the survey.

If you have any questions before you start, you can ask without any problem.

#Demographics (General questions for profiling the user)

1.1. City/Country of origin: _____

1.2. Gender:

- Male
- Female
- Prefer not to say

1.3. Age group:

- 0-25
- 25-40
- 40-65
- 65+

1.4. Area of employment:

- Unoccupied
- Culture
- Agriculture/Environment
- Computing
- Social/Training
- Student
- Engineering/Architecture
- ICT/Communication
- Other: _____

1.5. Do you have any sight issues?

- Yes
- No
- Prefer not to say

Pre-experience *(Preliminary questions to identify user preferences)*

2.1. How many times do you visit a cultural site or a museum during the year?

- None
- 1-2 times per year
- 3-5 times per year
- 5+ times per year

2.2. In a cultural site or museum, which type of visit support would you like to use? *(select one or more than one answer)*

- No support, I prefer a free visit
- A guided tour with a physical person
- A paper-based guide
- An audio-guide
- An application on a mobile phone or tablet
- An application on a touch totem or PC
- A digital touchable replica or 3D prints
- Something to play with

2.3. Do you know what an autochrome is?

- Yes, *can you explain?* _____ *(please write here)*
- No

2.4. Can you imagine what the experience in front of you is about?

- Yes, *can you explain?* _____ *(please write here)*
- No

**(max 10 min.)
Time For Experience**

Post experience *(Questions related to the user's considerations after experiencing the product)*

3.1. How much did you enjoy the experience of “Autochrome Viewer”?

(put an X on the degree of preference)

1 (Not at all) 2 3 4 5 (Very much)

3.2. What is the aspect you liked most out of this experience? *(select one or more than one answer)*

- The innovative installation
- The colors' overlapping
- The intimate experience though Occulators
- The photograph itself

3.3. Why? *(select one or more than one answer)*

- The colors' revelation
- Presenting an autochrome with modern technology
- Hands-on activity
- The innovative way of showing/explaining a photograph's composition
- (please write here extra comments done by user)*_____

3.4. What type of sensations did the “Autochrome Viewer” allow you to feel? *(select one or more than one answer)*

- Curiosity
- Wonder
- Complexity
- Excitement
- Confusion
- Disorientation
- Expectation
- Pleasure
- Relax
- Disturb
- Boredom
- More: _____ *(please write here extra comments from user)*

3.5. When looking through the Occulators, what are you able to see?

- Nothing
- The juxtaposition of the two layers
- Black and white image
- Each colored detail of the image

3.6. Did you see the juxtaposition of the two layers?

- Yes
- No

3.7. How do you consider the overlapping of images? *(put an X on the degree of preference)*

1 (Not good at all) 2 3 4 5 (Very good)

3.8. How is the level of color realism to you? *(put an X on the degree of preference)*

1 (Not appropriate) 2 3 4 5 (Appropriate)

3.9. How did you find the illumination level of the lightbox (middle-white cases)? *(put an X on the degree of preference)*

1 (Not appropriate) 2 3 4 5 (Appropriate)

3.10. In which sense? *(put an X on the degree of preference)*

- Too dark
- Too bright
- Dark enough
- Bright enough

3.11. Is the usage of the “Autochrome Viewer” easy to understand?

- Yes, *why?* _____ *(please write here)*
- No, *why?:* _____ *(please write here)*

3.12. How do you consider the whole “Autochrome Viewer” experience? (put an X on the degree of preference)

USEFULNESS FOR UNDERSTANDING THE OPTIC PRINCIPLES

1 (Not useful at all) 2 3 4 5 (Extremely useful)

USABILITY OF THE SYSTEM TO GET MORE ABOUT THE OPTIC PRINCIPLES

1 (Complex to use) 2 3 4 5 (Extremely easy to use)

DURATION OF THE EXPERIENCE

1 (Not appropriate) 2 3 4 5 (Appropriate)

3.13. Which moment of the experience you enjoyed the most?

_____ *(please write here)*

3.14. Which moment of the experience you didn’t enjoy?

_____ *(please write here)*

3.15. By the end, which are the main insights you got from the “Autochrome Viewer” experience? (select one or more than one answer)

- Understand the autochrome film technique
- Understand the difference between original and restored copies
- Understand the integrations of the conservative process
- Extra note: _____ *(please write here)*

3.16. How is the integration of inpainted content in the scene? (put an X on the degree of preference)

1 (Not good) 2 3 4 5 (Very good)

[PERCEIVE staff member]

Thank you for your time and cooperation!

Your feedback is precious and will help us in our research.

Observation

ONLY 4 PERCEIVE MEMBER STAFF

OBS # Autochrome Viewer (HLSU)

# Observation			
Questionnaire ID:_____ Operator:_____ Location: _____ Date:___/___/_____			
<p>0.1. Gender:</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Male <input type="checkbox"/> Female <input type="checkbox"/> Not expressed <input type="checkbox"/> _____	<p>0.2. Age group:</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Child <input type="checkbox"/> Teenager <input type="checkbox"/> Adult <input type="checkbox"/> Retired	<p>0.3. Location condition:</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Quiet <input type="checkbox"/> Confusing <input type="checkbox"/> Crowded but still quiet <input type="checkbox"/> _____	
<p>0.4. Does the user understand what she/he has to do?</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No, <i>why?</i> : _____(please write here)			
<p>0.5. Does the user ask for help?</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No, <i>why?</i> : _____(please write here)			
<p>0.6. Does the user seem active towards the installation or is it passive?</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Actively participate <input type="checkbox"/> Passively participate			
<p>0.7. Does the user talk while he/she experiences the installation?</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, with whom? _____ what does he/she say? _____ <input type="checkbox"/> No			
<p>0.8. How many participants are closeby?</p> <input type="checkbox"/> 1-2 persons <input type="checkbox"/> 2-4 persons <input type="checkbox"/> +4 persons			
<p>0.9. Is the user comfortable with the movements he/she has to do to experience it?</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No			
<p>0.10. How does the user behave around the installation?</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Looking through the Occulators <input type="checkbox"/> Moving around it <input type="checkbox"/> Standing still <input type="checkbox"/> Leaning over (up&down) <input type="checkbox"/> More: _____			
<p>0.11. What type of emotions does the user seem to feel?</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Curiosity			

- Wonder
- Complexity
- Excitement
- Confusion
- Disorientation
- Expectation
- Pleasure
- Relax
- Disturb
- Boredom
- Other: _____

0.12. How long does the user do this activity?

- Less than 1 minute
- 2 min. - 5 min.
- More than 5 minutes

Extra comments from Operator:

Annex 3 – Scream Time Machine Charts

Observation

Location

35 risposte

1.2. Gender

39 risposte

1.3. Age group

39 risposte

1.5. Do you have any sight issues?

39 risposte

Questionnaire

Pre-experience

2.1. How many times do you visit a cultural site or a museum during the year?

39 risposte

2.2. In a cultural site or museum, which type of visit support would you like to use? (select one or more than one answer)

39 risposte

2.3. How do you prefer to receive information in a cultural site or museum? (select one or more than one answer)

39 risposte

2.4. Have you ever seen the Munch's Scream in person?

39 risposte

2.5. What do you know about the Munch's Scream?

39 risposte

3.1. How much did you enjoy the experience of "Scream Time Machine"? (put an X on the degree of preference)

39 risposte

3.2. What is the aspect you liked most out of this experience? (select one or more than one answer)

39 risposte

3.3. Why? (select one or more than one answer)

39 risposte

3.4. How much did you like the TACTILE EXPLORATION of the Scream? (put an X on the degree of preference)

39 risposte

3.5. What type of sensations did the TACTILE EXPLORATION allow you to feel? (select one or more than one answer)

39 risposte

3.6. How does the projection of light behind the 3D TACTILE REPLICAS affect you?

34 risposte

3.7. And what about the VIDEO TUTORIAL: how would you consider the duration? (put an X on the degree of preference)

34 risposte

3.8. Is the language used in the VIDEO TUTORIAL easy to understand?

33 risposte

3.9. Let's play together! Are you able to retrace how many original Scream images you saw in the VIDEO TUTORIAL AND CARD GAME? (select one or more images)

37 risposte

3.8. How is the level of color realism to you? (put an X on the degree of preference)

36 risposte

3.10. Try to associate a sentiment to the following images of the Munch's Scream, you saw in the VIDEO TUTORIAL.

34 risposte

3.10. Try to associate a sentiment to the following images of the Munch's Scream, you saw in the VIDEO TUTORIAL.

34 risposte

3.11. How do you consider the CARD GAME? (put an X on the degree of preference)

3.12. Which moment of the CARD GAME do you enjoy the most?
(37 answers)

- Danger cards
- Participant was the danger and it was nice to have an interaction with the other players, to give them guidance.
- Finding the sequence
- The evolution over time
- The final
- Finding the correct order
- Trying to find the clue of each picture
- Deciding about the care cards
- Appreciated the small details
- Social component
- When I win.
- I think it depends on the role you have in the game. I enjoyed my role in the game, that being DANGER master.
- Final, with explanations
- Matching dangers with cares
- For the specialists, it's a funny game, but not easy
- care cards
- Danger sign
- Danger
- trying to figure out the dates.
- The end, and to see it in the right order!
- Danger vs care card
- at the end when the danger cards were quite finished
- The use of green and Red cards
- the whole game
- Playing the danger card
- When It ended - I so poorly
- the use of the danger cards

- When I have to find the correct sequence
- All game
- when I finally understood the colours
- Seeing the timeline of the pictures
- To find a care card for a particular danger card
- play with the danger card
- It was easy to see the damage of the theft, and it helps to arrange the chronology
- trying to tell the difference between the scream replicas
- when the daughters won
- The Moment she wins

3.13. Which moment of the CARD GAME you didn't enjoy?

37 risposte

3.14. By the end, which are the main insights you got from the "Scream Time Machine" experience?
(select one or more than one answer)

39 risposte

Annex 4 – Autochrome Viewer Charts

Observation

Location
23 responses

0.1. Gender

23 responses

0.2. Age group

23 responses

0.4. Does the user understand what she/he has to do?

23 responses

0.5. Does the user ask for help?

22 responses

0.6. Does the user seem active towards the installation or is it passive?

23 responses

0.7. Does the user talk while he/she experiences the installation?

23 responses

What does he/she say?

10 responses

Small notes about what they see. "Nothing", "Hmmm..."

I should figure out how to use this

Talks about what he knows about autochromes

Asking for instructions and/or explanations

mutters

with the instructor, asking questions

chats

He is asking questions about the autochromes and installation. very curious.

They speak in German so I don't understand

With whom she/he talking?

8 responses

Themselves
Herself
Giorgio
With Arthur
herself
other users around
He is talking with a friend
To the operator

0.8. How many participants are closeby?

22 responses

0.9. Is the user comfortable with the movements he/she has to do to experience it?

22 responses

0.10. How does the user behave around the installation?

23 responses

0.11. What type of emotions does the user seem to feel?

23 responses

0.12. How long does the user do this activity?

23 responses

Extra comments from Operator

11 responses

- Seems to know how to use the instrument
- The user wanted to know what he is looking at in the demonstrator. And to know what an tuochrome is. He wanted information, and was very curious.He looked at the originla autochrome a lot.
- User got a small introduction beforehand,
- The lights were on during the experience.
- There was confusion about what to see from the oculators, also about the individual components of the demonstrator.
- The user is a physicist so she was interested in the optical process. She even made comments about the lens. The lights were on
- She said she sees more colors from the squinter oculator. she really enjoyed seeing the original photograph.

Questionnaire

Pre-experience

Location

27 responses

1.1. City/Country of origin

27 responses

1.2. Gender

27 responses

1.3. Age group

27 responses

1.4. Area of employment

27 responses

1.5. Do you have any sight issues?

27 responses

2.1. How many times do you visit a cultural site or a museum during the year?

27 responses

2.2. In a cultural site or museum, which type of visit support would you like to use? (select one or more than one answer)

27 responses

2.3. Do you know what an autochrome is?

27 responses

2.4. Can you imagine what the experience in front of you is about?

27 responses

Post-experience

3.1. How much did you enjoy the experience of "Autochrome Viewer"? (put an X on the degree of preference)

27 responses

3.2. What is the aspect you liked most out of this experience? (select one or more than one answer)

27 responses

3.3. Why? (select one or more than one answer)

27 responses

3.4. What type of sensations did the "Autochrome Viewer" allow you to feel? (select one or more than one answer)

27 responses

3.5. When looking through the Occulators, what are you able to see?

27 responses

3.6. Did you see the juxtaposition of the two layers?

27 responses

3.7. How do you consider the overlapping of images? (put an X on the degree of preference)

26 responses

3.8. How is the level of color realism to you? (put an X on the degree of preference)

27 responses

3.9. How did you find the illumination level of the lightbox (middle-white cases)? (put an X on the degree of preference)

27 responses

3.10. In which sense? (put an X on the degree of preference)

26 responses

3.11. Is the usage of the "Autochrome Viewer" easy to understand?

27 responses

Why?

24 responses

Its not clear what we are looking for.

You need to know the background first.

You have to position yourself properly. The real autochrome does not require that. The colors in the original are most saturated and the contrast is higher.

I think it's easy to udnerstand, but it need isnructions, it is not fully intuitive

I got good instructions

I understand the need to protect the original

The quality of the oculators is not good enough. I didn't see color in the juxtaposition of layers, i only saw the color blobs but not the mixing of colors (for example, no skin tone).

Easy usability

3.12. How do you consider the whole “Autochrome Viewer” experience? (put an X on the degree of preference)

3.13. Which moment of the experience you enjoyed the most?

26 responses

- Seeing the whole picture (inpainting part)
- everything
- The blurred occlator.
- Nothing in particular
- The dyes/silver layers, and the original.
- This whole experience, I was curious how it works, the whole setup , altogether
- The silver color layers and the original photograph
- Seeing the original autochrome
- The two layers blending

3.14. Which moment of the experience you didn't enjoy?

27 responses

3.15. By the end, which are the main insights you got from the "Autochrome Viewer" experience?
(select one or more than one answer)

27 responses

Annex 5 – Perceive Isis’ Colours, Echoes of Loss

Questionnaire 1. Pre-test

- How old are you?
- What gender do you identify with? [male, female, non-binary, prefer not to answer, other]
- What is your city of origin?
- What is the highest level of education you have completed? [lower secondary, upper secondary, bachelor's degree, master's degree, doctorate]
- What is your current occupation (whether study or work)?
- To what extent is your educational background or professional profile connected to the cultural sector? Rate from 1 (Not at all) to 5 (Very much)
- In general, how easy is it for you to afford expenses for cultural and recreational activities? Rate from 1 (Not at all) to 5 (Very much)
- To what extent do these statements describe your relationship with cultural heritage? Rate from 1 (Not at all) to 5 (Very much)
 - Have you ever considered the cultural heritage of your city/region of origin as part of your identity?
 - In the past year, have you participated in cultural activities (visits to cultural institutions, reading, listening to or viewing informational materials about cultural heritage)?
 - In the past year, have you visited at least five cultural institutions (museums, cultural sites, theatres, etc.) near where you live?
 - In the past year, have you reflected on how cultural heritage could be irreparably damaged without adequate conservation strategies?
 - In the past year, have you thought that policymakers should pay greater attention to the protection and enhancement of cultural heritage?
 - In the past year, have you visited a cultural heritage site or institution and realized that it was not preserved or valued as it deserves?
 - In the past year, have you done personal research on a place or cultural institution you were about to visit?
 - In the past year, during a visit, did you try to use additional free informational materials (e.g., information sheets and panels, websites or online materials)?
 - In the past year, during a visit, did you try to use paid informational materials (e.g., audio guides or paid smartphone apps)?
 - In the past year, has a cultural experience led you to reflect on how people in the past lived and interacted with the places where you live or visit today?
 - In the past year, have you personally explored some of the themes or elements that emerged during a cultural visit?
 - In the past year, have you encouraged a family member, friend, or someone else to visit a cultural site that you particularly enjoyed?
 - In the past year, have you joined an association in the cultural heritage sector (e.g., Fondo Ambiente Italiano — FAI, International Council of Museums — ICOM, etc.)?
 - In the past year, have you signed a petition for the protection of cultural heritage?
 - In the past year, have you volunteered in the cultural sector (e.g., FAI, guide for a local institution, museum "friends" associations, etc.)?
 - In the past year, have you made donations to cultural sites, institutions, or organizations?
- Before today, did you know that Greco-Roman statues were originally painted?
- If yes, how would you describe your level of knowledge about this? [Likert scale from 1 to 5]

- To what extent do you agree with these statements? [select a value from: Strongly disagree, Disagree, Somewhat agree, Agree, Strongly agree]
 - Right now I would like to discuss cultural heritage topics with friends or family.
 - Right now I would like to know more about a collection I have visited.
 - Now I would like to support research and activities in the cultural sector (e.g., volunteering, donations).
 - I believe that citizens, as a community, can take care of cultural heritage.
 - I believe I can take care of cultural heritage through individual actions.
 - I believe I can make an important contribution as an individual so that citizens, together, can take care of cultural heritage.
 - In the past year I have supported or backed cultural events or similar initiatives.

Questionnaire 2. Post-test

- Please enter your email address (the same one you provided in the previous questionnaire)
- What emotions did this video evoke? Rate from 1 (Not at all) to 5 (Very much): Joy; Trust; Fear; Surprise; Sadness; Disgust; Anger; Anticipation
- What were, in your opinion, the most significant concepts from the opening video? Rate from 1 (Not at all) to 5 (Very much)
 - Greco-Roman statues were originally painted
 - An Egyptian goddess was venerated in Rome
 - In the past, traces of polychromy were erased because it was believed that ancient statues were white
 - The citizens of Pompeii rebuilt the temple after the earthquake of 62 CE
 - I can take care of cultural heritage with my presence, attention, and empathy
- If you want to discover the chemical composition of a pigment, what tools should I use? [Microscope, Imaging techniques, Spectrometer]
- Reorder the process of colour analysis and reconstruction, as presented in this exhibition:
 - Imaging techniques (UVL, ultraviolet luminescence; VIL, visible-induced luminescence)
 - Creation of mock-ups and use of AI
 - Analysis of historical and iconographic sources
 - Spectroscopic techniques (XRF, X-ray fluorescence; FORS, fiber optic reflectance spectroscopy)
 - Microscope
- Do you remember how imaging techniques support scientists? [a) By magnifying small traces of colour; b) By locating hidden pigments and dyes; c) By providing information on the chemical composition of pigments]
- How would you describe the way you felt after visiting this installation?
- In your opinion, what is the key message of this final installation?
- Did you like this concluding installation? [Likert scale from 1 to 5, each value is indicated with a star]
- If you indicated 3 stars or fewer, what did not convince you? What conclusions did you expect from this visit experience?
- To what extent do you agree with these statements? [select a value from: Strongly disagree, Disagree, Somewhat agree, Agree, Strongly agree]
 - Right now I would like to discuss cultural heritage topics with friends or family.
 - Right now I would like to know more about a collection I have visited.
 - Now I would like to support research and activities in the cultural sector (e.g., volunteering, donations).

- I believe that citizens, as a community, can take care of cultural heritage.
- I believe I can take care of cultural heritage through individual actions.
- I believe I can make an important contribution as an individual so that citizens, together, can take care of cultural heritage.
- In the future I would like to support or back cultural events or similar initiatives.
- What do you consider to be the most important concept you take away from this experience?
- In the future, we would like to stay in touch with you and ask you some questions about your relationship with cultural heritage. This can help to better understand how citizens take care of cultural heritage. If you agree, send an email to: sofia.pescarin@cnr.it.

Main Evaluation Results

What emotions did this video evoke? Rate from 1 (Not at all) to 5 (Very much)

Plutchik-like emotions (scaled 0–1)

What were, in your opinion, the most significant concepts from the opening video? Rate from 1 (Not at all) to 5 (Very much)

Question	True	False
If you want to discover the chemical composition of a pigment, what tools should I use?	81%	19%
Do you remember how imaging techniques support scientists?	67%	33%

Reorder the process of colour analysis and reconstruction, as presented in this exhibition: Imaging techniques (UVL, ultraviolet luminescence; VIL, visible-induced luminescence); Creation of mock-

ups and use of AI; Analysis of historical and iconographic sources; Spectroscopic techniques (XRF, X-ray fluorescence; FORS, fibre optic reflectance spectroscopy); Microscope

A value of 70% indicates that the participant correctly ordered: 1) source analysis; 2) archaeometry analysis; 3) mock-ups & AI.

Did you like this concluding installation?

Analysis of change in intention and in perceived efficacy. The column contain: average values for QST-C1, QST-C2, their difference, p-value, effect size and p-value after Holm-Bonferroni correction. The second table applies a ceiling correction, removing answers of those participants (n_{out}) who already provided 5/5 in QST-C1 and for whom there is thus no expected improvement. To be valid, $n_{in} \geq 36$.

Item	M_{pre}	M_{post}	Δ	p_{raw}	d	p_{Holm}
Discuss CH	3.90	4.03	0.13	0.109	0.196	0.326
Learn more	4.11	4.19	0.07	0.403	0.095	0.805

Support research	3.50	3.77	0.27	0.004*	0.367	0.022*
Collective efficacy	4.21	4.26	0.04	0.590	0.062	0.805
Individual efficacy	3.70	3.93	0.23	0.036*	0.244	0.178
Participative efficacy	3.99	4.14	0.16	0.08	0.214	0.321
General support	3.76	4.34	0.59	approx. 0.0*	0.499	0.001*

<i>Item</i>	n_{out}	n_{in}	M_{pre}	M_{post}	Δ	p_{raw}	d	p_{Holm}
Discuss CH	20	50	3.46	3.70	0.24	0.024*	0.335	0.055
Learn more	25	45	3.62	3.91	0.29	0.016*	0.381	0.055
Support research	14	56	3.12	3.50	0.38	0.001*	0.483	0.005*
Collective efficacy	33	37	3.51	3.81	0.30	0.024*	0.402	0.055
Individual efficacy	18	52	3.25	3.71	0.46	0.001*	0.528	0.004*
Participative efficacy	25	45	3.42	3.76	0.33	0.014*	0.404	0.055
General support	25	45	3.07	4.16	1.09	2.04e-6*	0.986	1.43e-5*